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Professor Xenophon Verykios, Editor
Applied Catalysis B: Environmental

3 July 2018

Dear Prof. Verykios,

We are resending you the revised manuscript entitled “Ni catalysts with La as promoter supported over Y- and Beta- zeolites for CO₂ methanation”, once considered all suggestions and comments arisen by Reviewers.

We are considering that the revised version is now ready for publication in Applied Catalysis B: Environmental.

Yours sincerely,

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AUTHORS' ANSWERS TO REVIEWERS (APCATB-D-18-01386)

Dear Editor,

Thank you very much for your letter including the suggestions by Reviewers to improve the quality of our manuscript. Following are listed the comments of reviewers with our answers and corrections inserted in red color. Also you can find a marked version of the new manuscript, in which we have indicated in blue color the amendments made, and in red color removal of previous text, according to Reviewers' suggestions. In the following, references to lines correspond to the Marked Copy of the manuscript.

Reviewers' comments and authors' answers.

Reviewer #1: This paper reports the CO₂ methanation on Ni/zeolite catalysts. The catalysts were well characterized using XRD, N₂ gas adsorption, uv-vis, TPR and XPS and catalytic activity and durability was evaluated. The experiments were carefully done and the reliable results were obtained in this study. The significant enhancement of the activity by La addition was also found in this study. Thus, some interesting results were included in this study. However, the mechanistic discussion may be insufficient; the role of La species and which Ni species are active are unclear. Thus, major revision is requested for publication of this paper. Individual comments are listed below.

Thank you very much for the general good evaluation of the manuscript. The commented weaknesses by the reviewer have been considered and amended as explained in the following.

#1 Fig. 3. Please comment on why the peaks at 385-390 °C peak appears only Ni/Na-Y or Ni/Na-BETA, not H-type ones.

Thank you. As the reviewer points out, there are no peaks at 385-390 °C in H-type samples, but peaks with a similar meaning are also observed for H-type catalysts in the range 405-450 °C. In fact, in all samples, the first peak (between 385 and 450 °C) is attributed to reduction of NiO located on the external surface of the zeolite. The appearance of that peak at 385 and 390 °C for Ni/Na-Y and Ni/Na-BETA catalysts is due to a general shift of the H₂-TPR profiles to lower temperatures with respect to their protonic counterpart (Ni/H-Y and Ni/H-BETA catalysts). This shift is associated with the addition of exchanged Na⁺, which enhances, as discussed in the manuscript, the reducibility of nickel (lines 256-259 and 278-288).

#2 Samples characterized. The authors characterized the samples containing Ni²⁺ species. However, the catalytically active species must be metallic nickel formed after H₂ pretreatment. The reviewer suggests characterizing also the catalysts after the reduction treatment for a better understanding of the catalysts used.

Thank you for this interesting issue. Following the reviewer's suggestion, further characterization of the reduced samples has been done. All reduced catalysts were characterized by XRD and new diffractograms have been incorporated in Figure 1 (Ni/zeolite catalysts) and Figure 6 (Ni-La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts). In all cases, the presence of elemental nickel (actually the active phase) was detected (lines 193-195 and 335-337) and crystallite sizes determined by Scherrer equation included in Table 2 and Table 3. The crystallite size of Ni resulted to be similar to that of NiO, confirming our previously drawn conclusions.

#3 T50. Please define the "T50".

T50 parameter is defined in the amended version as "the temperature at which 50% of CO₂ is converted". This information has been included in line 181.

#4 Fig. 5 CO₂ is not a product, but a reactant. The expression of "Products distribution" must be modified.

The reviewer is right, strictly speaking, in his comment. We named products, in a general way, to any species involved in the reaction, regardless of reactant or reaction product. To avoid confusion, in the revised version we have substituted "products distribution" for "C-species distribution" (lines 318 and 484). Accordingly, Y-axis titles of Figures 5 and 13 have been modified.

#5 Pore size distribution. It would be interesting if the authors discuss the change in the pore size distribution with Ni and/or La loading.

Thank you, we agree with the convenience of this discussion to verify some of our conclusions, although probably not new conclusions would be drawn on the discussion reported in this paper. In fact, textural properties of the samples were analyzed in a Micromeritics TRISTAR II 3020 equipment, without the possibility of achieving ultra-high vacuum (UHV), needed to determine the pore size distribution of such microporous materials. We consider the reviewer's comment for our future work.

#6 Fig. 13 is missing.

Thank you very much for detecting this mistake. Consistently, the Figure has been added to the revised manuscript (now is Figure 14).

#7 Active Ni species. The authors commented that the reduction of the size of NiO particles from 21.1 nm to 10.4 nm contributes to the increased activity. This size of NiO must be located on the outer surface of zeolite, not inside of pores. Please discuss the active Ni species for CO₂ methanation in more detail.

Thank you for this interesting issue. Indeed, the size of either NiO or Ni crystallites estimated from Scherrer equation refers to Ni particles that are located in the external surface of the zeolite (lines 197-204 and 343-348). The internally located Ni²⁺ is also considered active phase as long as it is able to be reduced at 500 °C for 1 h under 20%H₂/He flow (reduction conditions prior to reaction).

Nevertheless, considering the reviewer's comment, we have examined Ni particle size of La₂O₃ based catalysts by TEM and EDX mapping (lines 149-159 and lines 454-463). Both TEM micrographs and EDX maps are included in the new Figure 11, where Ni particles size located at the surface of Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA and Ni/Na-BETA catalysts has been calculated by measuring the size of at least 100 particles of several TEM images. It is worth to note that the size of Ni particles measured by TEM results in similar values to those estimated previously by XRD (17.7 vs. 20.1 nm and 10.1 vs. 10.4 nm, respectively), confirming that La₂O₃ increases the dispersion of nickel.

#9 Role of La. Significant enhancement of the catalytic activity was reported by the addition of La species in this paper. However, the mechanistic discussion of the role of La species is almost absent. Such discussion may improve the quality of this work.

Thanks to the reviewer for his valuable comment. We assume that a mechanistic discussion could improve the quality of this work. However, in order to perform the mechanistic study several experiments by FTIR would be needed in order to determine specifically the concrete role of lanthanum in the mechanism. Nevertheless, considering the characterization and activity results of this study, one can make an idea of what is the role of lanthanum. On the one hand, CO₂-TPD results reveal that lanthana addition provides a great amount of weak and medium strength basic sites, which translates in an activity enhancement. On the other hand, as recently reported by D. Wierzbicki et al. (2018) [new ref. 47], it seems that lanthanum not only acts as a provider of medium strength basic sites, but also as modifier of Ni properties for CO₂ adsorption. In that way, the addition of lanthana strongly modifies the electronic structure of nickel resulting in vast CO₂ adsorption over Ni⁰ and also leading to greater CO₂ conversion. The EDX map of Ni and La (Figure 11f), in which well-dispersed La in close contact with nickel is observed, may be representative of that interaction.

Reviewer #2: This paper studied the catalytic performance of protonic and Na-exchanged Y and BETA zeolite supported Ni catalysts for CO₂ methanation, and found BETA was a better support than Y. Subsequently, different loads of La₂O₃ were impregnated into Na-exchanged BETA zeolite, to evaluate the effect of promoter on its catalytic performance. It reveals that the La₂O₃ addition can increase the surface basicity and Ni dispersion of Ni/BETA, resulting in the increase of both activity and selectivity towards CH₄. Moreover, the performance of Ni-La₂O₃/BETA, reported in this work, is not superior to other Ni-based catalysts in the literatures and the novelty of this work should be clarified. The manuscript is well organized and written can be accepted after following revisions.

Thank you very much for the positive assessment of the manuscript. Following the comment on the performance of our catalysts related to other proposals in the literature, we have included the new Table 5, which compares activity results of catalysts prepared in this work and others reported in the literature. It can be observed that 10%Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalyst present similar values of CO₂ conversion and CH₄ selectivity to that observed for other promoted catalyst such as 14%Ni-7%Ce/USY.

#1 Graphical Abstract, the marks in the right figure should be checked carefully.

Thanks for your observation. Mistakes in the legends on the graph have been corrected.

#2 Figure 13 is missed in the manuscript.

We appreciate this observation. It was our mistake. The Figure has been included into the revised manuscript (now is Figure 14).

#3 In conclusion, "However, the reducibility of Ni is higher in the Ni/H-BETA than in the Ni/H-Y catalyst due to a major proportion of NiO species located on the outer surface of the catalyst." This cannot coincide with the description in page 11: "Ni/Na-BETA catalyst contains more reducible NiO/Ni²⁺ species inside the framework"

It seems to us that some misunderstanding is occurring with the reviewer' comment. Please, note that in lines 311-317 the activity of Ni/Na-BETA and Ni/Na-Y catalyst was compared, but

not being referred to Ni/H-BETA and Ni/H-Y. Just to avoid confusion, we have corrected the sentence in line 315 to “Ni/Na-BETA catalyst contains more Ni²⁺ species inside the framework”.

#4 The authors should explain what kind of new basic sites on Ni-La₂O₃-BETA at 640 °C in Figure 8.

As already explained in the original version (lines 371-373), “samples with 10% and 15% of La₂O₃ present one additional peak centered at ≈ 640 °C, which is assigned to bulk carbonate decomposition”, as also reported by other authors [43].

#5 Compared with the mesoporous oxides, zeolite supports have many disadvantages including high pressure drop, susceptible to plugging, strong water absorption, and so on. Thus, it seems not to be a suitable support in CO₂ methanation with high GHSV. The stability test should be done for long time.

Thank very much for this general comment. Various supports of Ni catalysts were under investigation for the CO₂ methanation, including Al₂O₃, TiO₂, La₂O₃, mixed oxides, and more recently others such as bentonite, hydrotalcites and zeolites. Former studies on Ni impregnated USY zeolite promoted with CeO₂ by Graca et al. (ref. 27) indicated that the increase of the amount of impregnated Ni increased the activity of the catalyst in CO₂ methanation reaction, due to higher amount of Ni⁰ species after reduction. The crucial point is if this increase of the active phase is more pronounced than other possible negative effects as those mentioned by the reviewer, which, in turn, can be modulated, as we are trying in the present paper.

The catalytic behavior of our catalysts is now compared with other reported in the literature (new Table 5), and discussion on this point has been added in the amended version (lines 498-507). Concerning stability, Figure 13 was missed in the previous version, and has been incorporated into the new version (now Figure 14), showing long stability of both CO₂ conversion and CH₄ selectivity, for at least 24 h of time of stream.

#6 The author may compare the performance of this Ni-La₂O₃-BETA with the reported ones.

Thank you for this suggestion. The performance comparison between Ni-La₂O₃/Na-BETA and other catalysts reported in the literature has been included in the new Table 5. Discussion on the activity of different catalysts listed in Table 5 has been given in lines 498-507.

#7 Some works on Ni-based catalyst and thermodynamic analysis for CO₂ methanation should be cited, such as Fuel Processing Technology 2015, 135: 34-46; RSC Advances, 2012, 2(6): 2358-2368.

A new paragraph concerning the thermodynamics equilibrium analysis of the CO/CO₂ methanation reactions has been included, together with the effect of different reaction parameters on conversion and selectivity. Both references are now included in the Introduction (refs. [4] and [5]).

Reviewer #4: In the manuscript titled 'Ni catalysts with La as promoter supported over Y- and Beta- zeolites for CO₂ methanation' by Quindimil et al., the authors present catalytic activity of zeolite catalyst in CO₂ methanation. This is very interesting manuscript and topic due to environmental issues but also because there is limited number of studies concerning zeolite based catalysts for CO₂ methanation. The presented data is abundant and accurate, making this work very interesting. However, manuscript is not free of mistakes. What is more, the authors should discuss certain aspects of the manuscript in more details. Therefore, I recommend to revise the manuscript before it can be published. Below I present my comments:

Thank you very much for the positive, general assessment of our manuscript by the reviewer.

#1: In general, the manuscript is lacking comparison of tested catalysts with materials described in literature, including zeolites (papers of Henriques et al.) or simpler catalytic systems (e.g. Ni supported on single oxides - alumina, silica etc.). Similar comment concerns lanthana promoted samples. Effect of lanthanum promotion on Ni-based catalyst in CO₂ methanation was already investigated (works of Wierzbicki et al.). Presented manuscript should refer to these papers.

Following the suggestion of the reviewer, we have included the new Table 5 in the revised manuscript, which compares activity results of catalysts prepared in this work with other reported in the literature. Table 5 shows that 10%Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalyst presents similar values of CO₂ conversion and CH₄ selectivity in comparison with other promoted catalyst such as 14%Ni-7%Ce/USY. Additionally, we have included the suggested paper as ref. [47] (line 493) in order to explain the effect of promoters on the catalytic behavior.

#2: The authors often explain catalytic activity via characterized properties of nickel oxide. However, the active phase for CO₂ methanation is metallic nickel, therefore much more information (which would support drawn conclusions) could be extracted from characterization of reduced samples. Did the authors perform such characterization?

Thank you very much for such interesting, opportune comment. Following the reviewer's recommendation, further characterization of the reduced samples has been done. All reduced catalysts have been characterized by XRD and the new diffractograms have been incorporated in Figure 1 (Ni/zeolite catalysts) and Figure 6 (Ni-La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts). For all cases, the presence of elemental nickel (actually the active phase) was detected (lines 193-195 and 343-348) and crystallite sizes were determined by Scherrer equation (Table 2 and Table 3). The crystallite size of Ni resulted to be similar to that of NiO, which supports drawn conclusions.

#3: While discussing UV-vis spectra (lines 212-213), the authors stated that bands at 670 and 750 nm were detected only for Ni/H-Y sample. In fact, spectra of Ni/H-Y catalyst show two small shoulders at 670 and 750 nm. In my opinion, the presence of such shoulders for other samples cannot be eliminated basing on the spectra presented in Fig. 2.

The reviewer is right in this appreciation. As explained in the manuscript, we attribute bands at 670 and 750 nm to the presence of Ni²⁺ located in hexagonal prisms (octahedral coordination). Those two bands are clearly observed for the sample with high amount of exchanged nickel, as revealed by H₂-TPR and also by the observed green color of the Ni/H-Y sample, which indicates the presence of nickel in octahedral coordination. On the contrary, the remaining three

samples with lower amount of exchanged nickel present a greenish-gray color. Therefore, that would explain why those two bands are not so clearly detected for the other catalysts, although its presence cannot be disregarded (lines 233-235, Figure 2).

#4: XRD results (line 173 and 301). The authors wrote that new phase of NiO or bunsenite was detected. I do not quite understand why the authors separated NiO from bunsenite, as the latter is mineral name of nickel oxide.

Thanks for the observation. Indeed, bunsenite is the mineral name of NiO. In order to avoid misunderstandings we have put in brackets the name of the mineral (lines 192 and 336).

#5: For Beta zeolite based catalysts H₂-TPR experiments showed that most of the nickel species is reduced at temperatures higher than 500 °C. Therefore, did the authors tried to reduce catalyst (prior to reaction) at higher temperatures? Could it improve catalytic activity?

In order to maintain the catalytic properties of the zeolitic support, catalysts were prepared by calcination at 550 °C during 4 h, what prevents the prepared catalysts from pore destruction and BET surface reduction. Therefore, prereduction has to be done at a temperature close to the calcination, without overpassing it, in order to avoid any change in the catalytic properties of the zeolite. Then, we consider 500 °C the maximum prereduction temperature and we did not try to reduce the catalyst at higher temperature

#6: The authors often refer to the dispersion of nickel or available NiO area (e.g. line 277, lines 284-285, lines 306-307), however, this expressions are not supported by experimental data. How the authors examined nickel dispersion or how they can support this information?

The reviewer is right, we did not calculate dispersion values of Ni supported in our catalysts. When we wrote about dispersion, we were referring to Ni particle size in the catalysts, as smaller particles would mean an increase in metal dispersion. Therefore, we have change this expressions in the text and we are now referring to Ni particle size instead of Ni dispersion. To measure the size of Ni crystals, we have analyzed the effect of La₂O₃ addition on this parameter by TEM and EDX mapping (lines 149-159 and lines 430-442). Both TEM micrographs and EDX maps are included in Figure 11. The Ni particles size of Ni/Na-BETA and Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts has been calculated by measuring the size of at least 100 particles of several TEM images. It is worth to note that the size of Ni particles measured by TEM results in similar values to those estimated previously by XRD (17.7 vs. 20.1 nm and 10.1 vs. 10.4 nm, respectively), confirming that La₂O₃ increases the dispersion of nickel.

#7: (lines 290-291). The authors wrote: 'CO yield, on the contrary, is somewhat superior for Ni/H-zeolite catalysts and reaches maximum values at 400 °C'. Data presented in Fig. 5 shows otherwise, as CO yield was smaller at 350 and greater at 400 and 450 °C for protonic samples with respect to Na⁺ exchanged ones.

The reviewer is right, it was our mistake in the interpretation of activity results and hence, the text has been amended (lines 318-323).

#8: While discussing XRD patterns of La-promoted samples, the authors stated that the lack of the reflections of La₂O₃ phase points to high dispersion of La species or formation of amorphous phase. The data presented in Fig. 6 shows that with increasing content of La the XRD patterns in 20-30 2θ region is lifted with respect to unpromoted sample, which points to

the increasing content of amorphous phase. Other point is if the authors checked the presence of other La-containing phases e.g. lanthanum carbonate, which could be formed during synthesis. This could explain CO₂ desorption peak associated with carbonates in CO₂-TPD profiles.

Thanks for the observation. As the reviewer points out, the XRD backgrounds of La containing samples are lifted in 25-35 ° 2θ region with respect to Na-BETA indicating a great fraction of an amorphous phase, so the text has been modified (lines 338-341). Despite having checked it with specific software, we did not detect the presence of other crystalline La phase such as lanthanum carbonate, which is believed to be a more stable phase than La₂O₃.

#9 In Fig. 7 the authors presented relationships between La₂O₃ content and textural parameters. However, the La₂O₃ content presented in Fig. 7 is not consistent with the data presented in Table 1. I believe that 5, 10 and 15 % were nominal contents of lanthana which differ from the real ones presented in Table 1.

The reviewer is right. The La₂O₃ content presented in Table 1 differs from the nominal content. For a better understanding of the effect of La₂O₃ impregnation on textural properties, the X-axis of Figure 7 has been modified showing the real content calculated by XRF instead of the nominal.

#10: (lines 396-400). The authors wrote: 'As general trend, the progressive increase in La₂O₃ loading leads to higher CO₂ conversions at every temperature...'. Conclusions presented in that paragraph are based on examination of only two La loadings (nominal 5 and 10%). I do not believe that this is enough to draw such general conclusions. What would be the case of catalysts loaded for instance with 3 or 7 wt.% of La₂O₃? How the authors could support that?

As the reviewer says, the conclusions drawn in that paragraph are based just on the analysis of two catalysts (5 and 10% loaded ones) and hence, the expression 'as general trend' must be removed (find correction in lines 470-473). We agree that in order to better determine the optimum loading of La₂O₃ might have been necessary testing additional catalysts with other loadings of La₂O₃ (more than three points). According to our results (Figure 12), a clear enhancement in activity is observed when La₂O₃ loading is increased from 5 to 10%, whereas for Ni-15La₂O₃ catalyst, no further improvement is observed. So, in our opinion the optimum La₂O₃ loading should be encountered close to 10% (either slightly above or below).

#11: In the presented manuscript there is no Fig. 13. It should be added to the manuscript.

We appreciate the reviewer' comment. The Figure has been added to the manuscript (now is Figure 14).

#12: Fig. S3 - It would be helpful if mass loss was presented in wt. %. This way it would give more information, as the loss of -1.5 mg does not say much if the initial mass of the sample is unknown.

The reviewer is right. Therefore, the mass loss has been presented in weight percentage instead of mg for a better interpretation of Figure S4.

Minor comments:

-Abstract (line 16): "(" at the beginning of the line

-section 2.2 (line 110): 'KV' instead of 'kV'

-section 3.1.2 (lines 288-289) Sentence: 'In fact, ...' is not clear

All these minor comments have been amended.

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1 **Ni catalysts with La as promoter supported over Y- and Beta- zeolites for**
2 **CO₂ methanation**

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9

10 **Abstract**

11 The hydrogenation of CO₂ into methane is considered a plausible process to storage renewable
12 energy in form of methane and reducing CO₂ anthropogenic emissions. Microporous solids
13 such as zeolites have been scarcely studied yet for this application. This study aims to evaluate
14 and compare the catalytic performance of zeolite (Y and BETA) supported Ni catalysts for CO₂
15 methanation. The physicochemical properties of the prepared catalysts were characterized
16 with XRD, BET, CO₂-TPD, H₂-TPR and XPS, and CO₂ methanation was carried out in a tubular
17 reactor at conditions of H₂/CO₂ = 4, GHSV = 10,000 h⁻¹ and temperatures from 200 to 500 °C.
18 Neutralization of both zeolites by Na⁺ ion exchange enhanced the CO₂ conversion as weaker
19 CO₂ adsorption sites and reducibility are promoted. BETA resulted in a better support than Y
20 zeolite due to the presence of more easily reducible Ni²⁺, which acts as precursor of active Ni⁰
21 accessible under reaction conditions. Indeed, the surface basicity and Ni dispersion of Ni/BETA
22 catalysts was considerably promoted by impregnation of different loads of La₂O₃, which
23 increase the amount of CO₂ adsorption sites and even active hydrogenation sites resulting in a
24 significant increase of activity and selectivity towards CH₄. The optimal Ni-10%La₂O₃/Na-BETA
25 formulation resulted in T₅₀ of 320 °C, CO₂ conversion of 65% at 350 °C, with almost total
26 selectivity to CH₄ and maintaining stability for more than 24 h.

27

28 *Keywords:*

29 Y-zeolite, BETA-zeolite, zeolite-supported Ni catalysts, La promoter, CO₂ methanation

30 **1. Introduction**

31 Anthropogenic CO₂ emissions from an energy system based on fossil fuels are the main cause
32 of climate change. It is estimated that annual CO₂ emissions will continue to increase due to
33 the global growing energy demand linked to the exponential increase in population. In fact,
34 the International Energy Agency (IEA) foresees 35.7 Gt of emitted CO₂ for 2040, a quantity far
35 from enough to avoid severe climate change [1].

36 The replacement of fossil energy by renewable energy is presented as the better alternative to
37 overcome this environmental challenge. In the near future this carbon-free sustainable energy
38 source is expected to play an important role in a mixed energy system. At present, however,
39 renewable energy sources remain considerably less efficient and therefore less profitable than
40 fossil energy sources. The lower efficiency of renewable energies is due, in part, to their
41 intermittency: wind and solar energy are fluctuating and have to be balanced for electric grid
42 stability purposes. For that reason, there is a growing interest in the development of
43 renewable energy storage forms [2].

44 Nowadays, the electrical power obtained from wind turbines and solar panels can be stored in
45 form of energy vector such as H₂ or CH₄. Hydrogen has a higher calorific value than methane
46 (33,900 vs. 13,249 kcal·kg⁻¹) and no CO₂ is formed during H₂ combustion. However, hydrogen
47 also presents some drawbacks compared to methane: (i) very low density, thus its storage is
48 considerably more expensive and (ii) infeasibility of large-scale transport due to incompatibility
49 of the current gas grid. Thus, the conversion of renewable energy into methane seems to be by
50 now a more suitable technology.

51 Valorization of CO₂ by hydrogenation is a promising alternative, not only because of the use of
52 renewable energy, but also because CO₂ anthropogenic emissions are reduced. Carbon dioxide
53 from flue gas can be combined with H₂ generated from renewable energies and converted
54 catalytically into methane or synthetic natural gas (SNG), according to the Sabatier reaction:

56 In fact, as a proof of concept, the e-gas plant of Audi Motor Company located in Werlte
57 (Germany) efficiently produces 1000 tons of SNG per year, combining renewable hydrogen and
58 concentrated CO₂ from a nearby biogas plant.

59 CO₂ is relatively difficult to be hydrogenated and indeed more difficult than CO, although
60 simultaneous methanation of CO and CO₂ is frequently encountered in a coexistent system,
61 where reactions between CO and CO₂ methanation are competing. A complete network of

62 possible reactions involved in the methanation of carbon dioxides is proposed in literature [3,
63 4]. On the basis of 10 reactions involved in the system with CO/CO₂/H₂/H₂O as reactants, a
64 systematic thermodynamic equilibrium analysis of the methanation reactions of carbon oxides
65 was reported by Gao et al. [4]. The effects of temperature, pressure, H₂/CO₂ (and H₂/CO) and
66 addition of water steam (and O₂, CH₄ and C₂H₄) on the methanation reactions were
67 comprehensively investigated [4, 5].

68 CO₂ methanation catalysts reported in literature normally consists of an active metal
69 supported on a metal oxide. Ru and Ni have been the most studied metals. On the one hand,
70 ruthenium is the most active and selective metal in CO₂ hydrogenation into methane. The only
71 disadvantage against nickel is the highest cost (more than 500 times, www.infomine.com). On
72 the other hand, nickel seems to be the most active and selective among the non-noble metals,
73 which is widely used in the industry due to its low cost. The main reported disadvantage of Ni-
74 based catalysts versus those based on Ru is deactivation due to interaction with CO and
75 formation of mobile nickel carbonyls that result in the metal sintering [6]. Nevertheless, the
76 stability of nickel can be improved by addition of promoters [7].

77 Concerning the support, mesoporous solids are usually used, such as Al₂O₃ [8], SiO₂ [9], TiO₂
78 [10], ZrO₂ [11], CeO₂ [12] and Ce-Zr mixed oxides [13]. On the contrary, microporous solids as
79 catalytic supports for CO₂ methanation have been scarcely studied in the literature for CO₂
80 methanation, e.g. Y zeolite supported Ni catalysts [14-16]. The main disadvantage of protonic
81 zeolites is their small capacity to adsorb CO₂. However, acidity of zeolites can easily be
82 neutralized by alkali ion exchange (as Na⁺ or K⁺), which are known to improve CO₂ adsorption
83 capacity [17-19]. In addition, due to their high specific surface area, it is possible to modulate
84 surface basicity by the impregnation of great loadings of CO₂ adsorbents such as alkaline earth
85 metals (e.g. Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ba²⁺) and rare earth metals (e.g. La₂O₃, CeO₂, Pr₂O₃). As far as we know,
86 BETA type zeolite has not been studied for this application. Therefore, this work is aimed to
87 prepare, characterize and compare the catalytic performance of protonic or Na-exchanged Y
88 and BETA zeolite supported Ni catalysts. Additionally, the effect of La₂O₃ as a CO₂ adsorption
89 promoter for the catalytic activity is investigated.

90

91 **2. Experimental**

92 *2.1. Catalysts preparation*

93 The synthesized samples consisted of zeolite supported Ni catalysts, some of them promoted
94 by La. On the one hand, three types of zeolites were used as a support supplied by Zeolyst

95 International: CBV100 (Na-Y, Si/Al = 2.6), CBV 400 (H-Y, Si/Al = 2.6) and CP814E (NH₄-BETA,
96 Si/Al 12.5). From NH₄-BETA, zeolite H-BETA and Na-BETA were synthesized as follows. The
97 protonic form of BETA zeolite was obtained by simple calcination at 550 °C for 4 h with a
98 heating rate of 1 °C·min⁻¹. The Na-BETA zeolite was prepared by the metal ion exchange
99 procedure: the required amount of NaNO₃ (Merck, 99.5%) was dissolved in deionized water
100 (0.5 M solution); then, NH₄-BETA was added to this solution (10 mL/g) and the suspension was
101 continuously stirred for 24 h at room temperature. During the preparation pH=7 was kept by
102 the addition of ammonia. After the ion exchange, the support was filtered, washed twice with
103 deionized water and dried at 110 °C overnight. This procedure was repeated twice and finally
104 the exchanged zeolite was calcined for 4 h at 550 °C with a heating rate of 1 °C·min⁻¹.

105 On the other hand, the incipient wetness impregnation procedure was used for preparing
106 Ni/zeolite catalysts. This method consisted in adding the Ni(NO₃)₂ solution (Sigma Aldrich,
107 99.99%) dropwise to zeolite support so that the solute was driven into pores by capillary
108 forces. Once an excess of solution is achieved, the mass transfer into the pores shifts to
109 diffusion instead of capillary forces (slower process). In all cases, the nominal content of nickel
110 was set at 10% and, after impregnation, the catalysts were calcined at 550 °C for 6 h with a
111 heating rate of 5 °C·min⁻¹. On the other hand, 5, 10 and 15% La₂O₃ promoted catalysts were
112 prepared by successive impregnations in LaNO₃·6H₂O (Sigma Aldrich, 99.0%) and NiNO₃·6H₂O
113 solutions. In total, 7 catalysts were prepared and nominated as in Table 1, where the
114 framework type, chemical composition and Si/Al ratios are shown.

115 TABLE 1

116 2.2. Characterization techniques

117 X Ray Diffraction (XRD). Crystallinity of the powder catalysts was measured by XRD on a
118 PANalytical Xpert PRO diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) and Ni filter. The
119 operating conditions were 40 kV and 40 mA and diffractograms were recorded from 5 to 70° 2
120 θ with 0.02° per second sampling interval. PANalytical X'pert HighScore specific software was
121 used for data treatment and JCPDS database was used to interpret the diffractograms.

122 N₂ physisorption. Textural properties of the samples were determined from N₂ adsorption-
123 desorption isotherms measured at 77 K using a Micromeritics TRISTAR II 3020 equipment. The
124 specific surface areas of microporous samples were calculated by complete BET equation
125 which assumes a defined number of nitrogen layers and positive values of C parameter. Pore
126 volumes were calculated by t-plot method and pore size distribution of only mesoporous solids

127 was determined using BJH method. The samples were previously degassed overnight under N₂
128 flow.

129 Diffuse Reflectance UV-vis. The oxidation states and the coordination of Ni species were
130 evaluated by DR UV-vis spectroscopy. UV-vis-NIR measurements were carried out in a *Varian*
131 *Cary 5000* apparatus coupled to a Diffuse Reflectance Internal 2500. The polycrystalline
132 samples were finely grinded and the spectra were recorded at room temperature in a range of
133 wave number among 200 and 2500 nm.

134 Hydrogen Temperature Programmed Reduction (H₂-TPR). The reducibility of the Ni/zeolite
135 catalysts was determined by TPR. The experiments were carried out on a Micromeritics
136 AutoChem 2920 instrument. Firstly, samples were pre-treated at 250 °C or 500 °C for 30 min
137 under Ar or 5%O₂/He flow in order to remove adsorbed or chemisorbed H₂O and CO₂,
138 respectively. The pre-treatment temperature of 500 °C was used for catalysts with La₂O₃. The
139 reducing gas flow was 50 mL·min⁻¹ of 5%H₂/Ar and the temperature was raised from 40 to
140 900°C with a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹. The water formed during reduction was trapped using
141 a cold trap and the hydrogen consumption was continuously monitored with a TCD detector.

142 CO₂ Temperature Programmed Desorption (CO₂-TPD). Total basicity and basic strength
143 distribution were evaluated by TPD-MS studies. Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument was
144 used coupled to a *MKS Cirrus* mass spectrometer. Samples were pre-treated at 500 °C for 60
145 min under He flow and then cooled down to 50 °C. Then, CO₂ adsorption step was performed
146 by feeding 50 cm³·min⁻¹ of 5%CO₂/He flow until saturation. Subsequently, the samples were
147 flushed out with helium for 60 min to remove physisorbed CO₂ from the surface. Finally,
148 desorption was carried out from 50 to 850 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹. The CO₂
149 desorption was continuously monitored with the mass spectrometer.

150 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM-STEM). TEM measurements were carried out at FEI
151 Titan Cubed G2 60-300 electron microscope at 200 kV equipped with a high-brightness X-FEG
152 Schottky field emission electron gun, a monochromator, CEOS GmbH spherical aberration (Cs)
153 corrector on the image side and a Super-X EDX system under high annular dark field (HAADF)
154 detector for Z contrast imaging in STEM conditions (camera length of 185 mm). The nominal
155 size of the electron probe used for STEM and EDX maps was 0.5 nm and the probe current
156 170pA and the semiconvergence angle was 14 mrad. High-angle annular dark-field HAADF
157 STEM images were collected with an inner detector radius of 63.5 mrad. The samples for the
158 TEM were prepared by dispersion into ethanol solvent and keeping the suspension in an

159 ultrasonic bath for 15 min, after a drop of suspension was spread onto a TEM copper grid (300
160 Mesh) covered by a holey carbon film followed by drying under vacuum.

161 2.3. CO₂ methanation experiments

162 CO₂ methanation reaction were performed in a downflow fixed bed reactor (D_{in} = 9 mm) and
163 the product distribution was analyzed with a gas chromatograph (Agilent 7890 B). The
164 catalysts were pre-treated at 500 °C for 1 h under 20%H₂/He flow (250 cm³·min⁻¹) and after
165 cooling down to 200 °C in inert gas, the reaction mixture was fed to the reactor with a 4:1:1.25
166 H₂:CO₂:He molar relation. The reaction temperature range explored was from 200 to 500 °C in
167 steps of 25 °C. The He, H₂, CO₂, CH₄ and CO concentrations at the reactor exit at every
168 temperature were monitored once steady state was reached. He, H₂, CH₄ and CO were
169 followed by MolSieve type columns, whereas CO₂ was followed by HayeSep type column.

170 The experiments were carried out at atmospheric pressure with 0.5 g of catalysts, which were
171 pelletized, grinded and sieved to obtain particles size 0.3 - 0.5 mm. The catalyst particles were
172 diluted to 50% with quartz particles in order to improve mass and heat transfer. Under these
173 conditions, GHSV and W/F_{A0} resulted in 10,000 h⁻¹ and 4.67 g·h·mol⁻¹ respectively. CO₂
174 conversion (X_{CO2}) and CH₄ (Y_{CH4}) yield were calculated as:

$$175 \quad X_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

176 while selectivities towards CH₄ (S_{CH4}) and CO (S_{CO}) were calculated as:

$$177 \quad S_{\text{CH}_4} = \frac{F_{\text{CH}_4}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{out}}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$178 \quad S_{\text{CO}} = \frac{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{out}}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

179 Also yields of CO₂ to CH₄ and CO can be determined as:

$$180 \quad Y_{\text{CH}_4} = \frac{F_{\text{CH}_4}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}}} \times 100 = S_{\text{CH}_4} \times X_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (5)$$

$$181 \quad Y_{\text{CO}} = \frac{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}}} \times 100 = S_{\text{CO}} \times X_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (6)$$

182 Finally, T₅₀ parameter is defined as the temperature at which 50% of CO₂ is converted.

183

184 **3. Results and discussion**

185 *3.1. Ni/zeolite catalysts*

186 3.1.1. Characterization

187 Figure 1 shows XRD patterns of the protonic zeolites (H-Y and H-BETA, Figure 1a and Figure 1b,
188 respectively) as well as of those exchanged with Na⁺. It can be observed that the diffractogram
189 of Na-BETA zeolite is almost identical to its counterpart, which means that the crystalline
190 nature of the zeolite was not modified after the incorporation of Na⁺. However, minor loss of
191 crystallinity can be detected when Na⁺ is incorporated in Y zeolite, as already revealed other
192 authors [19, 20]. Also, no Na₂O was detected in XRD spectra, assuring a successful exchange of
193 Na⁺ in both zeolites. After Ni impregnation, new diffraction peaks at 37.3, 43.3 and 62.9° 2θ
194 revealed the formation of NiO (bunsenite phase) in the impregnated samples [6] which are
195 marked with asterisks. As expected, the presence of elemental nickel instead of NiO was
196 detected for the samples reduced at 500 °C for 1h under 20%H₂/He, as revealed by XRD peaks
197 at 44.3 and 51.7 ° 2θ marked with squares [8].

198 **FIGURE 1**

199 The Ni crystallite sizes, estimated by the Scherrer equation, are displayed in Table 2. A smaller
200 crystallite size can be observed for Ni/H-Y catalyst when comparing to Ni/H-BETA catalyst,
201 which is related to differences in zeolitic structure: unlike BEA, FAU structure contains
202 accessible cavities for Ni particles that might result in higher metal dispersion over the outer
203 surface of the zeolite. In the same line, Na⁺ incorporation in BETA zeolite produces the
204 formation of bigger Ni crystallites due to the partial pore blockage, which results in less
205 accessible zeolitic framework [21]. Anyway, no significant differences are observed in the
206 crystallite size, which indicates similar dispersion of the surface Ni for all catalysts.

207 **TABLE 2**

208 The N₂ physisorption isotherms of H-Y and H-BETA zeolites are shown in Figure S1. In the case
209 of H-Y zeolite the shape of the isotherms is characteristic of a microporous solid: great amount
210 of N₂ is adsorbed at very low pressures by micropore filling and thereafter very little
211 adsorption takes place (isotherm type I according to IUPAC). However, a different isotherm
212 shape is observed for H-BETA zeolite: although a great amount of N₂ is adsorbed at very low
213 relative pressures, more N₂ is also adsorbed at intermediate pressures by multilayer filling
214 (isotherm type IV). The appearance of a hysteresis loop at relative pressures up to 0.65 for H-

215 BETA indicates the presence of mesoporous which are suitable for impregnation of high metal
216 loadings.

217 Textural properties of the prepared samples are also shown in Table 2. Regardless the
218 presence of Na⁺ and after Ni impregnation over H-Y and Na-Y zeolites, a notable decrease of
219 specific surface area (14 and 20%) and micropore volume (17 and 24%) is produced due to the
220 formation of NiO clusters that block the zeolite pores, which reduces the adsorption capacity
221 of the supports [22, 23]. On the other hand, a similar trend can be observed in the textural
222 properties of BETA zeolite after Ni addition, resulting in BET surface reduction of 17 and 19%
223 for H-BETA and Na-BETA, respectively. Additionally, a notorious decrease of both microporous
224 and mesoporous volume is observed. The highest reduction is seen when Ni is impregnated
225 over H-BETA, being microporous and mesoporous volume reduced a 29% and 37%,
226 respectively.

227 In order to determine the symmetry and the coordination of nickel species dispersed on the
228 zeolites, diffuse reflectance spectroscopy was carried out. Figure 2 shows UV-vis-NIR spectra of
229 Y and BETA zeolites after Ni impregnation. In the UV-visible region (from 200 to 800 nm), all
230 catalysts present bands centered at 270, 380, 420 and 720 nm, all of them characteristics of
231 NiO species. The band centered at the lowest wavelength is assigned to O²⁻ → Ni²⁺ metal to
232 ligand charge transfer, while the bands at intermediate and high wavelengths are assigned to
233 d-d electron transitions of Ni²⁺ in octahedral coordination inside NiO [23]. In addition, two
234 bands centered at 450 and 635 nm can be distinguished which correspond to d-d electron
235 transitions of Ni²⁺ exchanged in tetrahedral coordination inside zeolite framework [24-26]. The
236 green Ni/H-Y catalyst also presents bands at 670 and 750 nm, not so clearly detected in other
237 samples and which are assigned to d-d electron transition of Ni²⁺ ions in octahedral
238 coordination [21, 27, 28]. However, the presence of this Ni species cannot be disregarded for
239 the latter samples.

240 **FIGURE 2**

241 On the other hand, other two bands can be observed in the NIR domain (from 800 to 2500
242 nm). The wide band centered at 1150 nm is attributed to the ν_1 (³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}) transition of
243 octahedrally coordinated Ni²⁺ and appears in all spectra of prepared samples indicating the
244 presence of NiO. In contrast, the last band centered at 1410 nm is related to vibrations of
245 surface hydroxyl groups of zeolite supports [29] and, as expected, is less intense for Ni/Na-
246 zeolite catalysts than for Ni/H-zeolite catalysts.

247 The redox properties of the prepared samples were examined by H₂-TPR technique in order to
248 analyze the reducibility of different nickel species dispersed on each zeolite. Figure 3a and
249 Figure 3b show the H₂-TPR runs for Ni/Y and Ni/BETA catalysts, respectively. In line with UV-
250 vis-NIR results, the appearance of several peaks in TPR spectra indicates the presence of
251 various Ni species with different reducibility. On the one hand, four defined H₂ consumption
252 peaks can be observed for Ni/H-Y catalyst (Figure 3a). The peak at lowest temperature (450 °C)
253 can be attributed to reduction of surface NiO particles interacting with the zeolitic support,
254 whereas peaks located at 520 and 645 °C are attributed to reduction of tetrahedrally
255 coordinated Ni²⁺ species located on supercages and sodalite cages, respectively [22, 27, 28, 30,
256 31]. The peak at highest temperature, with a maximum at 730 °C, is related to reduction of
257 octahedrally coordinated Ni²⁺ exchanged in hexagonal prisms, as was confirmed by UV-visible.
258 On the other hand, a new peak can be distinguished at 385 °C for Ni/Na-Y catalyst. The
259 position of this reduction peak is similar to the observed in the nickel oxide sample (insight
260 Figure 3a), so it is associated with reduction of NiO particles weakly interacting with Na-Y
261 zeolite and located in the external surface. The shift to lower temperature of H₂-TPR profile
262 reveals that Ni/Na-Y is a more easily reducible catalyst than Ni/H-Y catalyst. This fact is related
263 to the donation of electrons from Na⁺ to nickel [21].

264

FIGURE 3

265 Focusing on BETA supported catalysts (Figure 3b), unlike zeolite H-Y, BETA zeolite is not
266 formed by cavities: its structure consists of a three-dimensional system of channels, so nickel
267 location is different to that observed in the zeolite Y. For Ni/BETA catalysts four H₂ reduction
268 peaks are also observed. The peaks at lowest temperatures, with maximums located close to
269 400 and 450 °C, are related to reduction of NiO with different interaction degree with the
270 support. The first peak at the lowest temperature is attributed to reduction of NiO placed on
271 the outer surface while the second peak is assigned to reduction of certain population of NiO
272 clusters with smaller size and higher interaction with the support [23, 32, 33]. In contrast,
273 peaks at highest temperatures indicate the presence of Ni²⁺ located at different sites: the peak
274 centered around 560 °C is related to reduction of pseudo-tetrahedral Ni²⁺, whereas the peak
275 located between 620 and 655 °C is related to Ni²⁺ in hexagonal prisms [25, 26, 34-36]. In line
276 with Y zeolite based catalysts, shift of TPR profile to lower temperatures can be observed in
277 Ni/Na-BETA due to the above mentioned effect.

278 With the aim of quantifying the amount of Ni²⁺ reducible at temperatures below 500 °C,
279 additional TPR tests of reduced samples were carried out (Figure S2). The pre-reduction was
280 done under the same conditions used for the reductions prior to the activity tests: 500 °C for

281 1h with 20%H₂/He. As expected, TPR profiles of all catalysts exhibited a single H₂ consumption
282 peak between 600 and 700 °C, which is associated with reduction of exchanged nickel. The
283 amount of reduced nickel during pre-reduction process is quantified in the last column of
284 Table 2. Note that the percentage of reducible Ni²⁺ is above 90% for all catalysts, except for
285 Ni/H-Y (43%), which showed a notable peak at 680 °C. This means that almost all nickel is
286 getting reduced during activity tests for Ni/Na-Y, Ni/H-BETA and Ni/Na-BETA catalysts. Finally,
287 it is worth to mention that calculated H₂/NiO ratios are between 0.9 and 1.1 for all the
288 prepared catalysts, i.e., Ni²⁺ is the only reducible specie.

289 3.1.2. CO₂ methanation tests

290 The performances of the prepared catalysts were evaluated by analyzing the obtained CO₂
291 conversions and CH₄ yields. It must be noted that, in all cases, CO was the only secondary
292 product and that the carbon balance closed within ±5%. First, Figure 4 compares the catalytic
293 activity at increasing temperatures of protonic and sodium zeolites containing Ni. As a general
294 trend, it can be clearly noticed that the presence of exchanged Na⁺ in both zeolitic frameworks
295 leads to greater CO₂ conversions in the range of studied temperatures. This effect is more
296 pronounced for Y zeolite supported samples. In fact, the light-off T₅₀ curve of Ni/Na-Y catalyst
297 shifts 30 °C to lower temperatures, while light-off curve of Ni/Na-BETA catalyst is only shifted
298 15 °C. The greater activity of these catalysts, as already explained in H₂-TPR section (Figure 3),
299 is not only in line with the reducibility enhancement but also with the presence of weak CO₂
300 adsorption sites in Na-based catalysts. According to previous studies, the interaction between
301 CO₂ and the support is improved by the presence of the alkali metal, resulting in a promoted
302 CO₂ activation [21].

303 **FIGURE 4**

304 By comparing CO₂ conversions of Na⁺ free catalysts, greater activity is found for the Ni/H-BETA
305 catalyst. On the one hand, Ni/H-Y sample (T₅₀ = 415 °C) contains more internally located Ni
306 species providing higher metal dispersion; however, Ni/H-BETA (T₅₀ = 393 °C) sample presents
307 a greater amount of reducible Ni species at 500 °C (95% vs. 43%) which are considered the
308 active phase for CO₂ methanation [27, 37]. Therefore, the higher activity of Ni/H-BETA
309 catalysts could be related to a larger available Ni⁰ area during methanation reaction, as
310 revealed H₂-TPR results shown in Figure S2.

311 In contrast, when comparing Na-exchanged supported catalysts, similar CO₂ conversions are
312 observed in all range of studied temperatures. In both cases, 50% of CO₂ conversion occurs
313 around 380 °C and the maximum CO₂ conversions are reached at 450 °C (X_{CO₂} = 73%). Although

314 Ni/Na-Y catalyst has greater reducibility, according to the H₂-TPR results, Ni/Na-BETA catalyst
315 contains more Ni²⁺ species inside the framework which could provide higher dispersion.
316 Therefore, the same CO₂ methanation activity shown by both catalysts is explained by the
317 presence of similar available surface of active phase during reaction.

318 C-species distribution at the reactor exit for the prepared catalysts is illustrated in Figure 5. It
319 can be observed that the highest CH₄ yield is reached at 450 °C, being Na⁺ containing catalysts
320 more productive than Ni/H-zeolite catalysts. CO yield, on the contrary, is somewhat lower for
321 Ni/H-zeolite catalysts at 350 °C and somewhat higher at 400 °C. Regardless the reaction
322 temperature, methane yield of the samples reflects the following order: Ni/Na-BETA > Ni/Na-Y
323 > Ni/H-BETA > Ni/H-Y. Thus, Ni/Na-BETA catalyst results in the more active and productive
324 catalyst, showing maximum CO₂ conversion and CH₄ yield values of 73 and 71%, respectively.
325 Indeed, the best catalytic performance of this catalyst is attributed to the enhanced CO₂
326 adsorption and to the higher dispersion of reducible Ni species.

327 **FIGURE 5**

328 *3.2. Effect of La₂O₃ addition*

329 3.2.1. Characterization

330 XRD spectra of calcined and reduced Na-BETA supported Ni catalysts after the impregnation of
331 different amounts of La₂O₃ (5, 10 and 15%) are displayed in Figure 6. XRD spectra of calcined
332 catalysts show peaks at 37.3, 43.3 and 62.9° 2θ, whereas spectra of reduced catalysts show
333 peaks at 44.3 and 51.7 ° 2θ. The former correspond to NiO (bunsenite phase), while the latter
334 are characteristic of elemental Ni. However, the absence of La₂O₃ characteristic diffraction
335 peaks at 30.0, 39.5 and 46.1° 2θ corresponding to La₂O₃ suggests the formation of an
336 amorphous phase. In fact, the XRD backgrounds of La containing samples are lifted in 25-35 °
337 2θ region with respect to Na-BETA sample, indicating a greater proportion of amorphous
338 material.

339 **FIGURE 6**

340 Table 3 shows Ni crystallite sizes of La-containing catalysts calculated by the Scherrer equation.
341 It can be noticed that Ni dispersion increases with the addition of La₂O₃ loadings; i.e., the
342 higher the content of La₂O₃, the smaller the Ni crystallite size. In fact, the addition of 15% of
343 La₂O₃ to the Ni/Na-BETA catalyst reduces the surface Ni crystallite size from 20.1 to 7.1 nm,
344 providing higher active phase dispersions, since La₂O₃ acts as a thermal stabilizer of Ni [7, 38,
345 39]

346

TABLE 3

347 N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K of La-containing Ni/Na-BETA catalysts, as well as
348 isotherms of Na-BETA support are included in Figure S3 (Supplementary Material). Similar
349 isotherm shapes are observed in all cases (type I and type IV isotherms combination),
350 suggesting that lanthana addition does not modify considerably the textural properties of Na-
351 BETA zeolite.

352 The external surface areas together with pore volumes are summarized in Table 3. It can be
353 observed that impregnation of increasing loadings of La₂O₃ results in a progressive decrease of
354 the external surface area, which means that impregnated lanthana is located in the outer
355 surface of the zeolite. In fact, external surface area decreases from 224.9 m²·g⁻¹ in the Na-BETA
356 catalyst down to 132.6 m²·g⁻¹ in the 15% lanthana impregnated catalyst. In the same line,
357 specific surface area also decreases with metal content, as it can be observed in Figure 7. On
358 the other hand, regarding the pore volume, a similar trend is observed: the higher the metallic
359 load supported on the zeolite, the lower the pore volume, due to a partial blockage of pores
360 [22, 23, 40]. It is worth to mention that almost no difference can be observed between 15%
361 and 10% La₂O₃ loaded catalysts.

362

FIGURE 7

363 The basicity of different La₂O₃/Na-BETA samples was measured by TPD using CO₂ as probe gas.
364 CO₂-TPD profiles in Figure 8 shows that all these samples contain different CO₂ desorption
365 sites. According to desorption temperature, three different basic sites are detected: weak (T <
366 150 °C), medium (T = 150-550 °C) and strong (T > 550 °C) [7, 41, 42]. For 5%La₂O₃/Na-BETA
367 sample, two peaks centered at 100 and 190 °C are observed, which are attributed to CO₂
368 desorption from weak (surface OH⁻) and medium (acid-base Lewis pairs) basic sites, whereas
369 samples with 10 and 15% of La₂O₃ present one additional peak centered at 640 °C, which is
370 assigned to bulk carbonate decomposition [43]. However, this strongly attached CO₂ does not
371 participate in the CO₂ methanation, since it is desorbed at temperatures above those of
372 reaction. CO₂ desorption quantification obtained from TPD spectra reveal that lanthana
373 impregnation over Na-BETA results in a considerable increase of the surface basicity due to the
374 formation of new basic sites with different strength. Thus, the higher the La₂O₃ content, the
375 higher the number and strength of basic sites.

376

FIGURE 8

377 The effect of La₂O₃ addition on distribution and reducibility of Ni species dispersed on the
378 catalysts was determined by H₂-TPR. Before carrying out these experiments, catalysts were

379 degasified for 30 min with 5%O₂/He at 500 °C in order to remove weakly chemisorbed CO₂.
380 Then, H₂ consumption was followed by a TCD detector and, additionally, strongly attached CO₂
381 desorption was followed by mass spectrometry. The H₂-TPR spectra and CO₂ MS profiles of
382 samples with different lanthana content are shown in Figure 9. Below 500 °C, a main H₂
383 consumption peak with a maximum close to 400 °C is observed for all catalysts, which is
384 attributed to reduction of NiO located in the external surface of the zeolite [32, 33]. Above 500
385 °C, in contrast, the growing mass 44 signal (drawn in dashed line) confirms strongly attached
386 CO₂ desorption and hence, the recorded TCD signal cannot be attributed only to H₂
387 consumption. Nevertheless, the peak appearing above 600 °C is also related to reduction of
388 Ni²⁺ located inside BEA framework [36].

389 **FIGURE 9**

390 When comparing H₂-TPR profiles of the lanthana based catalysts, a shift to higher
391 temperatures with increasing the La₂O₃ loading is observed. This suggests that the presence of
392 La₂O₃ strengthens the interaction between nickel and the support, due to an increase of the
393 nickel polarization [38, 44]. From integration of TPR profiles up to 500 °C, the reducibility of
394 the samples was estimated and reflects this order: Ni/5La₂O₃/Na-BETA > Ni/10La₂O₃/Na-BETA
395 > Ni/15La₂O₃/Na-BETA. Therefore, the 5% La₂O₃ loaded catalyst presents the highest
396 reducibility. Note that H₂/NiO values are above the stoichiometric ratio, among 1.1 and 1.4,
397 since CO₂ is desorbed during H₂-TPR tests, as demonstrated in Figure 9.

398 In order to analyze the nature and surface distribution of La and Ni species, XPS measurements
399 were carried out. Figures 10a and 10b show XPS spectra corresponding to Ni 2p and La 3d core
400 levels for fresh and used catalysts, respectively. First, for fresh Ni/Na-BETA catalyst (insight
401 Figure 10a), Ni 2p_{3/2} region reveals two peaks at ≈ 854.5 and ≈ 857 eV together with a broad
402 shake-up satellite peak at ≈ 862 eV. The main peak at lowest binding energies is attributed to
403 NiO weakly interacting with Na-BETA zeolite, whereas the second one corresponds to the Ni²⁺
404 cation in exchangeable positions [25, 45]. No peak corresponding to reduced nickel (Ni⁰) at ≈
405 853 eV was detected. On the other hand, La₂O₃ addition to Ni/Na-BETA catalysts reveals a new
406 main peak in the La3d_{5/2} region at ≈ 835.7 and a satellite peak at ≈ 838.9 eV. Note that these
407 peaks, assigned to supported La³⁺ [41], intensify with La₂O₃ content, which indicates a
408 progressive increase of the La on the surface. Additionally, a main peak at ≈ 852.4 eV together
409 with its satellite peak at 856.3 are shown in La 3d_{3/2} - Ni 2p_{3/2} region, also corresponding to
410 La³⁺. Regardless the amount of La added in the catalysts, XPS spectra recorded after reaction
411 showed similar binding energies of La³⁺, i.e., La₂O₃ does not suffer from relevant changes after

412 reaction and no Ni⁰ was observed, which indicates that nickel is easily passivated after reaction
413 at ambient temperature [46] (see insight Figure 10b).

414 **FIGURE 10**

415 From integration of XPS spectra, surface carbon content as well as Ni/Si and Ni/La atomic
416 ratios of fresh and used Ni-La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts were calculated and data is summarized in
417 Table 4. It should be noticed that the content of surface carbon remains similar after reaction
418 in all cases suggesting that no coke was formed during reaction tests. As deduced from Table 4,
419 Ni/Si and La/Si atomic ratios increase with La₂O₃ content, i.e., La₂O₃ addition improves NiO
420 dispersion. This trend is in agreement with XRD results according to which a decrease of NiO
421 crystallite size with La₂O₃ loading was observed. Finally, samples submitted to reaction suffer
422 from a slight decrease of Ni/Si ratio and a small increase of La/Si ratio, probably due to Ni
423 sintering during catalytic tests.

424 **TABLE 4**

425 The effect of lanthana on nickel dispersion was also analyzed by transmission electron
426 microscopy. Figures 11a and 11d show TEM micrographs of reduced Ni/Na-BETA and Ni-
427 10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts, respectively. Unlike lanthana particles, in those images, Ni particles
428 are clearly observable. Notice that no changes occur in the morphology of nickel particle
429 (spherical) with the impregnation of 10% of La₂O₃. Nevertheless, changes in the particle size
430 distribution are observed (visualized and calculated from at least 100 particles of several TEM
431 images), being the distribution notably narrower for La containing sample. This suggests that
432 lanthana, as structural promoter, controls the growth of nickel particle during calcination.
433 Indeed, smaller Ni particles are observed for Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA, as it presents an average
434 particle size of 10.1 nm (close to the 10.4 nm observed in Table 3 for the same catalyst
435 estimated by Scherrer equation), whereas in Ni/Na-BETA catalyst an average of 17.7 nm can be
436 observed (similar to 20.1 nm presented in Table 2, again estimated by Scherrer equation).
437 Therefore, in agreement with XRD and XPS results, lanthana addition enhances nickel
438 dispersion.

439 As presence of lanthana was not detectable by TEM, additionally, STEM combined with EDX-
440 elemental mapping was performed. This technique is suitable to differentiate between two or
441 more elements, since provides high resolution element mapping. STEM images together with
442 EDX maps of Ni/Na-BETA and Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts are displayed in Figures 11b-11c
443 and 11e-11f, respectively. By comparing STEM image and Ni mapping (red colored) of Ni/Na-
444 BETA sample, it is confirmed that Ni is dispersed as spherical particles. Interestingly, EDX map

445 of Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalyst shows that La (green colored) is homogeneously dispersed
446 partially covering the surface of the zeolite and in close contact with nickel. Similar
447 homogeneous dispersion of La₂O₃ supported on Al₂O₃ has already been reported by Z. Boukha
448 et al. [41].

449 **FIGURE 11**

450 3.2.2. Activity and stability

451 Figure 12 shows the effect of La₂O₃ content on CO₂ conversion and the temperature-
452 dependent equilibrium conversion in a dashed line. The onset temperature for CO₂
453 methanation is 250 °C and thermodynamic equilibrium is reached for every catalyst. The
454 required temperatures for X_{CO₂} = 50% are 322, 330, 334 and 381°C for Ni-10La₂O₃, Ni-15La₂O₃,
455 Ni-5La₂O₃ and Ni/Na-BETA catalyst, respectively. The increase in La₂O₃ loading from 5 to 10%
456 leads to higher CO₂ conversions at every temperature, which suggests that the related gain in
457 basicity results in the desired promoter effect. However, although the increase in lanthana
458 nominal content (from 5 to 10%) leads to greater activity, impregnation of La₂O₃ loadings
459 above 10% seems not to be necessary since non enhancement in CO₂ methanation is
460 observed.

461 According to characterization results, the higher CO₂ methanation activity of Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-
462 BETA catalyst in comparison to Ni/Na-BETA catalyst is related to the greater amount of smaller
463 Ni particles (8.7 against 20.1 nm) and to the presence of a considerable amount of weak and
464 medium basic sites (16 vs. 1 μmol·g⁻¹). Also, 10% lanthana loaded catalyst reveals highest
465 reducibility, according to H₂-TPR results. On the other hand, the slight decrease in catalytic
466 activity observed for Ni-15La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalyst is associated with the lower textural
467 properties and reducibility shown in Figure 9.

468 **FIGURE 12**

469 In Figure 13 the C-species distribution at 300, 350 and 400 °C is shown for Ni/Na-BETA and Ni-
470 10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts. As in the case of Ni/zeolite catalysts, CO from RWGS was the only
471 detected by-product being the carbon balance closed between 95 – 105%. It can be observed
472 that CH₄ yield is increased and that CO yield is considerably reduced by addition of 10% of
473 La₂O₃ for all studied temperatures. The greatest difference among product yields occurs at the
474 reaction temperature of 350 °C: CH₄ yield increases from 30 to 65%, whereas CO yield
475 decreases from 4 to 0.4%. In line with characterization results, the better catalytic
476 performance observed in lanthana containing catalyst is related to a higher amount of active
477 sites where CO₂ can be adsorbed, dissociated and then hydrogenated to methane, according

478 to dissociative mechanism [37]. Moreover, according to Wierzbicki et al. [7, 47], lanthanum
479 addition not only provides new medium strength basic sites, but also modifies Ni properties
480 enhancing its CO₂ adsorption capacity. Therefore, it can be concluded that La₂O₃ addition
481 clearly promotes the CO₂ conversion and the CH₄ yield.

482 **FIGURE 13**

483 Activity comparison between catalysts prepared in this work with others recently reported in
484 literature is shown in Table 5 [8, 9, 27, 47]. In general, it can be observed that the addition of a
485 promoter enhances notably the catalytic activity for each formulation. For instance, the
486 addition of V₂O₅ to Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts improves considerably nickel dispersion and prevents
487 coke deposition [8], whereas CeO₂ impregnation on Ni/MCM-41 catalyst results in additional
488 CO₂ activation leading to higher conversion [9]. I. Graça et al. studied the performance of a
489 formulation analogous to ours, using CeO₂ (redox promoter) instead of La₂O₃ (structural
490 promoter) and Y zeolite instead of BETA zeolite. It can be observed that activity of the
491 promoted catalysts (14Ni-7Ce/USY and 10Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA) is similar, being slightly lower
492 for 14Ni-7Ce/USY catalyst due to a smaller spacial time (W/FA₀).

493 **TABLE 5**

494 Finally, the stability of the most active catalyst was evaluated after 24h on stream at 350 °C
495 (see Figure 14). Note that CO₂ conversion decreases slightly with time. This deactivation could
496 be related to both active site sintering and coke formation. The second hypothesis was
497 dismissed carrying out a thermo-gravimetric test in 5%O₂/He of the aged catalyst according to
498 which no relevant loss of mass was observed related to coke oxidation (not shown). After 10h-
499 on-stream, anyway, it seems that catalytic activity remains quite stable since similar CO₂
500 conversions are observed. In addition, the catalyst is very stable in terms of selectivity: non
501 decrease in CH₄ selectivity is observed after 24 h on stream.

502 **FIGURE 14**

503

504 **4. Conclusions**

505 The catalytic performance of Y- and BETA-zeolites supported Ni catalysts for CO₂ methanation
506 has been compared and additionally, the effect of La₂O₃ addition as promoter has been
507 evaluated.

508 The reducibility and dispersion of Ni species play an important role in CO₂ methanation: the
509 higher the value of these properties, the better the catalytic performance. Ni is more dispersed

510 in the form of NiO and Ni²⁺ species on H-Y than on H-BETA due to its higher crystallinity and a
511 more accessible framework. However, the reducibility of Ni is higher in the Ni/H-BETA than in
512 the Ni/H-Y catalyst due to a major proportion of NiO species located on the outer surface of
513 the catalyst. After reduction at 500 °C, H-BETA zeolite supported Ni catalysts present a higher
514 surface of reduced nickel (the active phase for CO₂ methanation) and hence, this leads to a
515 superior activity and selectivity.

516 Neutralization of both Y- and BETA-zeolites by addition of exchanged Na⁺ improves the
517 catalytic performance (T₅₀ decreases in 30 and 15 °C, respectively). This enhancement is not
518 only due to a greater reducibility, but also to the generation of some weak basicity that
519 improves CO₂ adsorption over the zeolite. Although not big differences in CO₂ conversions are
520 observed comparing Ni/Na-Y and Ni/Na-BETA catalysts, the latter achieves more selectivity
521 towards CH₄ than Ni/Na-Y. Therefore, it can be concluded that Ni/Na-BETA is the best catalyst
522 among those here studied to efficiently carry out the hydrogenation of CO₂ into methane.

523 According to the physicochemical properties of the samples, the addition of increasing
524 loadings of La₂O₃ to Ni-zeolite catalysts promotes dispersion into smaller Ni particles and
525 improves the CO₂ adsorption capacity of the zeolite. These enhancements in the surface
526 basicity and the Ni dispersion provide a greater amount of both basic and active sites, over
527 which CO₂ can be adsorbed and then hydrogenated into CH₄. In fact, double CO₂ conversion
528 with eventually total selectivity towards CH₄ can be achieved especially at low and
529 intermediate temperatures with Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA, which results in the optimal
530 composition. In contrast, higher loading than 10% La₂O₃ do not achieve additional
531 enhancement of the catalytic performance, since detrimental of the textural properties
532 exceeds the beneficial effect of CO₂ adsorption and hydrogenation sites. After 24 h on stream,
533 this formulation has proven to be quite stable in terms of activity and selectivity.

534

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540

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672

673 **Table and Figure Captions.**

674 **Table 1.** Nomenclature and chemical composition of the prepared catalysts.

675 **Table 2.** Physico-chemical properties of supports and Ni catalysts.

676 **Table 3.** Physico-chemical properties of Ni-La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts.

677 **Table 4.** Surface composition by XPS of the Ni-La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts, before and after
678 reaction.

679 **Table 5.** Comparison between the activity results achieved by the prepared Ni/BETA catalysts
680 and by those (unpromoted and promoted) reported in literature by other authors.

681

682 **Figure 1.** XRD patterns of (a) Y-zeolite supported catalysts (calcined and reduced) and (b) BETA-
683 zeolite supported catalysts (calcined and reduced).

684 **Figure 2.** UV-vis-NIR spectra of Ni/zeolite catalysts.

685 **Figure 3.** TPR profiles of (a) Y-zeolite (protonic and sodium) supported Ni catalysts and (b)
686 BETA-zeolite (protonic and sodium) supported Ni catalysts.

687 **Figure 4.** Effect of temperature on CO₂ conversion for (a) Y-zeolite (protonic and sodium)
688 supported catalysts and (b) BETA-zeolite (protonic and sodium) supported catalysts.

689 **Figure 5.** CO₂ conversion and C-species distribution at the reactor exit for Ni/zeolite catalysts at
690 350, 400 and 450 °C.

691 **Figure 6.** XRD patterns of calcined and reduced Ni/Na-BETA catalysts with different content of
692 La₂O₃.

693 **Figure 7.** Effect of lanthana incorporation onto Na-BETA on the specific surface area and pore
694 volume.

695 **Figure 8.** CO₂-TPD profiles of Na-BETA promoted with different lanthana loadings.

696 **Figure 9.** Evolution of H₂-TPR and the MS 44 signal with temperature for La₂O₃-promoted
697 Ni/Na-BETA catalysts.

698 **Figure 10.** XPS spectra for La₂O₃-promoted Ni/Na-BETA catalysts; (a) fresh, (b) after reaction.

699 **Figure 11.** TEM micrographs (a and d), STEM images (b and e) and EDX maps (c and f) of Ni/Na-
700 BETA and Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts.

701 **Figure 12.** Light-off curves of La₂O₃-promoted Ni/Na-BETA catalysts.

702 **Figure 13.** CO₂ conversion and C-species distribution at the reactor exit for Ni/Na-BETA and Ni-
703 10La₂O₃/Ni-BETA catalysts at 300, 350 and 400 °C.

704 **Figure 14.** Evolution of (a) CO₂ conversion and (b) selectivity to CH₄/CO, with time-on-stream
705 over 24 hours for Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalyst.

706

TABLE 1

707

Catalyst label	Framework	Si/Al ^a	Na (wt. %) ^a	Ni (wt. %) ^a	La ₂ O ₃ (wt. %) ^a
Ni/H-Y	FAU	2.5	1.4	9.5	-
Ni/Na-Y	FAU	2.6	6.0	9.9	-
Ni/H-BETA	BEA	12.4	0.0	9.2	-
Ni/Na-BETA	BEA	11.9	1.4	9.5	-
Ni-5La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	BEA	12.2	1.4	9.6	3.2
Ni-10La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	BEA	12.7	1.3	7.8	7.4
Ni-15La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	BEA	12.3	1.2	7.3	12.0

708

^a Determined by XRF.

709

710

711

712

TABLE 2

713

Sample	τ_{Ni} (nm) ^a	S_{BET} (m ² ·g ⁻¹) ^b	V_{micro} (cm ³ ·g ⁻¹) ^c	V_{meso} (cm ³ ·g ⁻¹) ^c	Reducible Ni ²⁺ at 500 °C (%) ^d
H-Y	-	720.5	0.24	0.07	-
Ni/H-Y	17.0	621.1	0.20	0.10	43
Na-Y	-	832.1	0.29	0.02	-
Ni/Na-Y	19.8	665.9	0.22	0.05	91
H-BETA	-	587.3	0.17	0.60	-
Ni/H-BETA	19.1	485.3	0.12	0.38	95
Na-BETA	-	513.6	0.13	0.38	-
Ni/Na-BETA	20.1	415.7	0.10	0.32	98

714

^a Estimated by Scherrer equation.

715

^b Calculated by complete BET equation.

716

^c Determined by application of t-Plot method.

717

^d Calculated from H₂-TPR profiles. Reduction conditions: 500 °C for 1h with 20%H₂/He.

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722

TABLE 3

723

Sample	τ_{Ni} (nm) ^a	S_{EXT} (m ² ·g ⁻¹) ^b	V_{micro} (cm ³ ·g ⁻¹) ^b
Na-BETA	-	224.9	0.13
Ni/Na-BETA	20.1	191.4	0.1
Ni-5La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	12.5	156.8	0.09
Ni-10La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	8.7	142.3	0.08
Ni-15La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	7.1	132.6	0.07

724

^a Estimated by Scherrer equation.

725

^b Determined by application of t-Plot method.

726

727

728

729

TABLE 4

730

Catalyst	Before reaction			After reaction		
	C (at. %)	Ni/Si	La/Si	C, at. %	Ni/Si	La/Si
Ni/Na-BETA	3.0	0.030	-	3.0	0.025	-
Ni-5La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	2.9	0.035	0.012	3.9	0.031	0.013
Ni-10La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	2.8	0.068	0.032	2.4	0.067	0.037
Ni-15La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	3.3	0.110	0.063	2.2	0.086	0.067

731

732

733

TABLE 5

734

Catalyst ^a	Total flow cm ³ ·min ⁻¹	Feed ratio (H ₂ /CO ₂ /Inert)	GHSV (h ⁻¹)	W/FA ₀ (g _{cat} ·h·mol ⁻¹)	X _{CO2} at 350 °C (%)	S _{CH4} at 350 °C (%)	Ref.
20NiO/Al ₂ O ₃	150	12/3/5	NA	1.7	42	97	[8]
20NiO-5V ₂ O ₅ /Al ₂ O ₃	150	12/3/5	NA	1.7	76	> 99	[8]
15Ni/MCM-41	250	36/9/10	15000	1.6	50	95	[9]
15Ce-15Ni/MCM-41	250	36/9/10	15000	1.6	60	97	[9]
15Ni-HT	100	12/3/5	12000	ND	74	99	[7]
15Ni2La-HT	100	12/3/5	12000	ND	78	98	[7]
14Ni/USY	250	36/9/10	43000	1.6	42	93	[27]
14Ni-7Ce/USY	250	36/9/10	43000	1.6	57	> 95	[27]
10Ni/Na-BETA	250	16/4/5	10000	4.7	33	88	This work
10Ni-10La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	250	16/4/5	10000	4.7	65	99	This work

735

^aHT = hydrotalcite; MCM-41 = mesostructured silica; USY = ultra-stable Y

736

737

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Highlights

- Ni supported on Y- and BETA-zeolites in their proton- and sodium-exchanged form have been prepared, characterized and tested in CO₂ methanation.
- The Na⁺ ion exchanged zeolites, BETA in more extent, weakens the CO₂ adsorption and enhances reducibility, thus achieving higher CO₂ conversion.
- Incorporation of La₂O₃ by impregnation increases basicity and enhances Ni dispersion, resulting in a significant increase of CO₂-to-CH₄ activity.
- The optimal Ni-10%La₂O₃/Na-BETA formulation resulted in T₅₀ of 320 ° C, with stable CO₂-to-CH₄ conversion of 65% at 350 °C for 24 h on stream.

Supplementary Material

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1 **Ni catalysts with La as promoter supported over Y- and Beta- zeolites for**
2 **CO₂ methanation**

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9

10 **Abstract**

11 The hydrogenation of CO₂ into methane is considered a plausible process to storage renewable
12 energy in form of methane and reducing CO₂ anthropogenic emissions. Microporous solids such
13 as zeolites have been scarcely studied yet for this application. This study aims to evaluate and
14 compare the catalytic performance of zeolite (Y and BETA) supported Ni catalysts for CO₂
15 methanation. The physicochemical properties of the prepared catalysts were characterized with
16 XRD, BET, CO₂-TPD, H₂-TPR and XPS, and CO₂ methanation was carried out in a tubular reactor
17 at conditions of H₂/CO₂ = 4, GHSV = 10,000 h⁻¹ and temperatures from 200 to 500 °C.
18 Neutralization of both zeolites by Na⁺ ion exchange enhanced the CO₂ conversion as weaker CO₂
19 adsorption sites and reducibility are promoted. BETA resulted in a better support than Y zeolite
20 due to the presence of more easily reducible Ni²⁺, which acts as precursor of active Ni⁰ accessible
21 under reaction conditions. Indeed, the surface basicity and Ni dispersion of Ni/BETA catalysts
22 was considerably promoted by impregnation of different loads of La₂O₃, which increase the
23 amount of CO₂ adsorption sites and even active hydrogenation sites resulting in a significant
24 increase of activity and selectivity towards CH₄. The optimal Ni-10%La₂O₃/Na-BETA formulation
25 resulted in T₅₀ of 320 °C, CO₂ conversion of 65% at 350 °C, with almost total selectivity to CH₄
26 and maintaining stability for more than 24 h.

27

28 *Keywords:*

29 Y-zeolite, BETA-zeolite, zeolite-supported Ni catalysts, La promoter, CO₂ methanation

30 1. Introduction

31 Anthropogenic CO₂ emissions from an energy system based on fossil fuels are the main cause of
32 climate change. It is estimated that annual CO₂ emissions will continue to increase due to the
33 global growing energy demand linked to the exponential increase in population. In fact, the
34 International Energy Agency (IEA) foresees 35.7 Gt of emitted CO₂ for 2040, a quantity far from
35 enough to avoid severe climate change [1].

36 The replacement of fossil energy by renewable energy is presented as the better alternative to
37 overcome this environmental challenge. In the near future this carbon-free sustainable energy
38 source is expected to play an important role in a mixed energy system. At present, however,
39 renewable energy sources remain considerably less efficient and therefore less profitable than
40 fossil energy sources. The lower efficiency of renewable energies is due, in part, to their
41 intermittency: wind and solar energy are fluctuating and have to be balanced for electric grid
42 stability purposes. For that reason, there is a growing interest in the development of renewable
43 energy storage forms [2].

44 Nowadays, the electrical power obtained from wind turbines and solar panels can be stored in
45 form of energy vector such as H₂ or CH₄. Hydrogen has a higher calorific value than methane
46 (33,900 vs. 13,249 kcal·kg⁻¹) and no CO₂ is formed during H₂ combustion. However, hydrogen
47 also presents some drawbacks compared to methane: (i) very low density, thus its storage is
48 considerably more expensive and (ii) infeasibility of large-scale transport due to incompatibility
49 of the current gas grid. Thus, the conversion of renewable energy into methane seems to be by
50 now a more suitable technology.

51 Valorization of CO₂ by hydrogenation is a promising alternative, not only because of the use of
52 renewable energy, but also because CO₂ anthropogenic emissions are reduced. Carbon dioxide
53 from flue gas can be combined with H₂ generated from renewable energies and converted
54 catalytically into methane or synthetic natural gas (SNG), according to the Sabatier reaction:

56 In fact, as a proof of concept, the e-gas plant of Audi Motor Company located in Werlte
57 (Germany) efficiently produces 1000 tons of SNG per year, combining renewable hydrogen and
58 concentrated CO₂ from a nearby biogas plant.

59 CO₂ is relatively difficult to be hydrogenated and indeed more difficult than CO, although
60 simultaneous methanation of CO and CO₂ is frequently encountered in a coexistent system,
61 where reactions between CO and CO₂ methanation are competing. A complete network of

62 [possible reactions involved in the methanation of carbon dioxides is proposed in literature \[3,](#)
63 [4\]. On the basis of 10 reactions involved in the system with CO/CO₂/H₂/H₂O as reactants, a](#)
64 [systematic thermodynamic equilibrium analysis of the methanation reactions of carbon oxides](#)
65 [was reported by Gao et al. \[4\]. The effects of temperature, pressure, H₂/CO₂ \(and H₂/CO\) and](#)
66 [addition of water steam \(and O₂, CH₄ and C₂H₄\) on the methanation reactions were](#)
67 [comprehensively investigated \[4, 5\].](#)

68 CO₂ methanation catalysts reported in literature normally consists of an active metal supported
69 on a metal oxide. Ru and Ni have been the most studied metals. On the one hand, ruthenium is
70 the most active and selective metal in CO₂ hydrogenation into methane. The only disadvantage
71 against nickel is the highest cost (more than 500 times, www.infomine.com). On the other hand,
72 nickel seems to be the most active and selective among the non-noble metals, which is widely
73 used in the industry due to its low cost. The main reported disadvantage of Ni-based catalysts
74 versus those based on Ru is deactivation due to interaction with CO and formation of mobile
75 nickel carbonyls that result in the metal sintering [36]. Nevertheless, the stability of nickel can
76 be improved by addition of promoters [74].

77 Concerning the support, mesoporous solids are usually used, such as Al₂O₃ [85], SiO₂ [69], TiO₂
78 [710], ZrO₂ [118], CeO₂ [129] and Ce-Zr mixed oxides [130]. On the contrary, microporous solids
79 as catalytic supports for CO₂ methanation have been scarcely studied in the literature for CO₂
80 methanation, e.g. Y zeolite supported Ni catalysts [141-163]. The main disadvantage of protonic
81 zeolites is their small capacity to adsorb CO₂. However, acidity of zeolites can easily be
82 neutralized by alkali ion exchange (as Na⁺ or K⁺), which are known to improve CO₂ adsorption
83 capacity [174-196]. In addition, due to their high specific surface area, it is possible to modulate
84 surface basicity by the impregnation of great loadings of CO₂ adsorbents such as alkaline earth
85 metals (e.g. Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ba²⁺) and rare earth metals (e.g. La₂O₃, CeO₂, Pr₂O₃). As far as we know,
86 BETA type zeolite has not been studied for this application. Therefore, this work is aimed to
87 prepare, characterize and compare the catalytic performance of protonic or Na-exchanged Y
88 and BETA zeolite supported Ni catalysts. Additionally, the effect of La₂O₃ as a CO₂ adsorption
89 promoter for the catalytic activity is investigated.

90

91 **2. Experimental**

92 *2.1. Catalysts preparation*

93 The synthesized samples consisted of zeolite supported Ni catalysts, some of them promoted by
94 La. On the one hand, three types of zeolites were used as a support supplied by Zeolyst

95 International: CBV100 (Na-Y, Si/Al = 2.6), CBV 400 (H-Y, Si/Al = 2.6) and CP814E (NH₄-BETA, Si/Al
96 12.5). From NH₄-BETA, zeolite H-BETA and Na-BETA were synthesized as follows. The protonic
97 form of BETA zeolite was obtained by simple calcination at 550 °C for 4 h with a heating rate of
98 1 °C·min⁻¹. The Na-BETA zeolite was prepared by the metal ion exchange procedure: the required
99 amount of NaNO₃ (Merck, 99.5%) was dissolved in deionized water (0.5 M solution); then, NH₄-
100 BETA was added to this solution (10 mL/g) and the suspension was continuously stirred for 24 h
101 at room temperature. During the preparation pH=7 was kept by the addition of ammonia. After
102 the ion exchange, the support was filtered, washed twice with deionized water and dried at 110
103 °C overnight. This procedure was repeated twice and finally the exchanged zeolite was calcined
104 for 4 h at 550 °C with a heating rate of 1 °C·min⁻¹.

105 On the other hand, the incipient wetness impregnation procedure was used for preparing
106 Ni/zeolite catalysts. This method consisted in adding the Ni(NO₃)₂ solution (Sigma Aldrich,
107 99.99%) dropwise to zeolite support so that the solute was driven into pores by capillary forces.
108 Once an excess of solution is achieved, the mass transfer into the pores shifts to diffusion instead
109 of capillary forces (slower process). In all cases, the nominal content of nickel was set at 10%
110 and, after impregnation, the catalysts were calcined at 550 °C for 6 h with a heating rate of 5
111 °C·min⁻¹. On the other hand, 5, 10 and 15% La₂O₃ promoted catalysts were prepared by
112 successive impregnations in LaNO₃·6H₂O (Sigma Aldrich, 99.0%) and NiNO₃·6H₂O solutions. In
113 total, 7 catalysts were prepared and nominated as in Table 1, where the framework type,
114 chemical composition and Si/Al ratios are shown.

115 **TABLE 1**

116 *2.2. Characterization techniques*

117 X Ray Diffraction (XRD). Crystallinity of the powder catalysts was measured by XRD on a
118 PANalytical Xpert PRO diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) and Ni filter. The
119 operating conditions were 40 ~~kV~~ kV and 40 mA and diffractograms were recorded from 5 to 70°
120 2 θ with 0.02° per second sampling interval. PANalytical X'pert HighScore specific software was
121 used for data treatment and JCPDS database was used to interpret the diffractograms.

122 N₂ physisorption. Textural properties of the samples were determined from N₂ adsorption-
123 desorption isotherms measured at 77 K using a Micromeritics TRISTAR II 3020 equipment. The
124 specific surface areas of microporous samples were calculated by complete BET equation which
125 assumes a defined number of nitrogen layers and positive values of C parameter. Pore volumes
126 were calculated by t-plot method and pore size distribution of only mesoporous solids was
127 determined using BJH method. The samples were previously degassed overnight under N₂ flow.

128 Diffuse Reflectance UV-vis. The oxidation states and the coordination of Ni species were
129 evaluated by DR UV-vis spectroscopy. UV-vis-NIR measurements were carried out in a *Varian*
130 *Cary 5000* apparatus coupled to a Diffuse Reflectance Internal 2500. The polycrystalline samples
131 were finely grinded and the spectra were recorded at room temperature in a range of wave
132 number among 200 and 2500 nm.

133 Hydrogen Temperature Programmed Reduction (H_2 -TPR). The reducibility of the Ni/zeolite
134 catalysts was determined by TPR. The experiments were carried out on a Micromeritics
135 AutoChem 2920 instrument. Firstly, samples were pre-treated at 250 °C or 500 °C for 30 min
136 under Ar or 5%O₂/He flow in order to remove adsorbed or chemisorbed H₂O and CO₂,
137 respectively. The pre-treatment temperature of 500 °C was used for catalysts with La₂O₃. The
138 reducing gas flow was 50 mL·min⁻¹ of 5%H₂/Ar and the temperature was raised from 40 to 900°C
139 with a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹. The water formed during reduction was trapped using a cold
140 trap and the hydrogen consumption was continuously monitored with a TCD detector.

141 CO₂ Temperature Programmed Desorption (CO₂-TPD). Total basicity and basic strength
142 distribution were evaluated by TPD-MS studies. Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument was
143 used coupled to a *MKS Cirrus* mass spectrometer. Samples were pre-treated at 500 °C for 60 min
144 under He flow and then cooled down to 50 °C. Then, CO₂ adsorption step was performed by
145 feeding 50 cm³·min⁻¹ of 5%CO₂/He flow until saturation. Subsequently, the samples were flushed
146 out with helium for 60 min to remove physisorbed CO₂ from the surface. Finally, desorption was
147 carried out from 50 to 850 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹. The CO₂ desorption was
148 continuously monitored with the mass spectrometer.

149 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM-STEM). TEM measurements were carried out at FEI
150 Titan Cubed G2 60-300 electron microscope at 200 kV equipped with a high-brightness X-FEG
151 Schottky field emission electron gun, a monochromator, CEOS GmbH spherical aberration (Cs)
152 corrector on the image side and a Super-X EDX system under high annular dark field (HAADF)
153 detector for Z contrast imaging in STEM conditions (camera length of 185 mm). The nominal size
154 of the electron probe used for STEM and EDX maps was 0.5 nm and the probe current 170pA
155 and the semiconvergence angle was 14 mrad. High-angle annular dark-field HAADF STEM images
156 were collected with an inner detector radius of 63.5 mrad. The samples for the TEM were
157 prepared by dispersion into ethanol solvent and keeping the suspension in an ultrasonic bath
158 for 15 min, after a drop of suspension was spread onto a TEM copper grid (300 Mesh) covered
159 by a holey carbon film followed by drying under vacuum.

160 2.3. CO₂ methanation experiments

161 CO₂ methanation reaction were performed in a downflow fixed bed reactor (D_{in} = 9 mm) and the
 162 product distribution was analyzed with a gas chromatograph (Agilent 7890 B). The catalysts were
 163 pre-treated at 500 °C for 1 h under 20%H₂/He flow (250 cm³·min⁻¹) and after cooling down to
 164 200 °C in inert gas, the reaction mixture was fed to the reactor with a 4:1:1.25 H₂:CO₂:He molar
 165 relation. The reaction temperature range explored was from 200 to 500 °C in steps of 25 °C. The
 166 He, H₂, CO₂, CH₄ and CO concentrations at the reactor exit at every temperature were monitored
 167 once steady state was reached. He, H₂, CH₄ and CO were followed by MoISieve type columns,
 168 whereas CO₂ was followed by HayeSep type column.

169 The experiments were carried out at atmospheric pressure with 0.5 g of catalysts, which were
 170 pelletized, grinded and sieved to obtain particles size 0.3 - 0.5 mm. The catalyst particles were
 171 diluted to 50% with quartz particles in order to improve mass and heat transfer. Under these
 172 conditions, GHSV and W/F_{A0} resulted in 10,000 h⁻¹ and 4.67 g·h·mol⁻¹ respectively. CO₂
 173 conversion (X_{CO₂}) and CH₄ (Y_{CH₄}) yield were calculated as:

$$174 \quad X_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

175 while selectivities towards CH₄ (S_{CH₄}) and CO (S_{CO}) were calculated as:

$$176 \quad S_{\text{CH}_4} = \frac{F_{\text{CH}_4}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{out}}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$177 \quad S_{\text{CO}} = \frac{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{out}}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

178 Also yields of CO₂ to CH₄ and CO can be determined as:

$$179 \quad Y_{\text{CH}_4} = \frac{F_{\text{CH}_4}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}}} \times 100 = S_{\text{CH}_4} \times X_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (5)$$

$$180 \quad Y_{\text{CO}} = \frac{F_{\text{CO}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{in}}} \times 100 = S_{\text{CO}} \times X_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (6)$$

181 Finally, T₅₀ parameter is defined as the temperature at which 50% of CO₂ is converted.

182 **3. Results and discussion**

183 *3.1. Ni/zeolite catalysts*

184 3.1.1. Characterization

185 Figure 1 shows XRD patterns of the protonic zeolites (H-Y and H-BETA, Figure 1a and Figure 1b,
186 respectively) as well as of those exchanged with Na⁺. It can be observed that the diffractogram
187 of Na-BETA zeolite is almost identical to its counterpart, which means that the crystalline nature
188 of the zeolite was not modified after the incorporation of Na⁺. However, minor loss of
189 crystallinity can be detected when Na⁺ is incorporated in Y zeolite, as already revealed other
190 authors [169, 2017]. Also, no Na₂O was detected in XRD spectra, assuring a successful exchange
191 of Na⁺ in both zeolites. After Ni impregnation, new diffraction peaks at 37.3, 43.3 and 62.9° 2θ
192 revealed the formation of ~~a new~~ NiO ~~or~~ (bunsenite phase) in the impregnated samples [63, 51],
193 which are marked with asterisks. As expected, the presence of elemental nickel instead of NiO
194 was detected for the samples reduced at 500 °C for 1h under 20%H₂/He, as revealed by XRD
195 peaks at 44.3 and 51.7 ° 2θ marked with squares [85].

196 FIGURE 1

197 The ~~NiO~~Ni crystallite sizes, estimated by the Scherrer equation, are displayed in Table 2. A
198 smaller crystallite size can be observed for Ni/H-Y catalyst when comparing to Ni/H-BETA
199 catalyst, which is related to differences in zeolitic structure: unlike BEA, FAU structure contains
200 accessible cavities for Ni[⊖] particles that might result in higher metal dispersion over the outer
201 surface of the zeolite dispersion. In the same line, Na⁺ incorporation in BETA zeolite produces the
202 formation of bigger Ni[⊖] crystallites due to the partial pore blockage, which results in less
203 accessible zeolitic framework [2118]. Anyway, no significant differences are observed in the
204 crystallite size, which indicates similar dispersion of the surface Ni for all catalysts.

205 TABLE 2

206 The N₂ physisorption isotherms of H-Y and H-BETA zeolites are shown in Figure S1. In the case
207 of H-Y zeolite the shape of the isotherms is characteristic of a microporous solid: great amount
208 of N₂ is adsorbed at very low pressures by micropore filling and thereafter very little adsorption
209 takes place (isotherm type I according to IUPAC). However, a different isotherm shape is
210 observed for H-BETA zeolite: although a great amount of N₂ is adsorbed at very low relative
211 pressures, more N₂ is also adsorbed at intermediate pressures by multilayer filling (isotherm
212 type IV). The appearance of a hysteresis loop at relative pressures up to 0.65 for H-BETA
213 indicates the presence of mesoporous which are suitable for impregnation of high metal
214 loadings.

215 Textural properties of the prepared samples are also shown in Table 2. Regardless the presence
216 of Na⁺ and after Ni impregnation over H-Y and Na-Y zeolites, a notable decrease of specific
217 surface area (14 and 20%) and micropore volume (17 and 24%) is produced due to the formation

218 of NiO clusters that block the zeolite pores, which reduces the adsorption capacity of the
219 supports [2219, 230]. On the other hand, a similar trend can be observed in the textural
220 properties of BETA zeolite after Ni addition, resulting in BET surface reduction of 17 and 19% for
221 H-BETA and Na-BETA, respectively. Additionally, a notorious decrease of both microporous and
222 mesoporous volume is observed. The highest reduction is seen when Ni is impregnated over H-
223 BETA, being microporous and mesoporous volume reduced a 29% and 37%, respectively.

224 In order to determine the symmetry and the coordination of nickel species dispersed on the
225 zeolites, diffuse reflectance spectroscopy was carried out. Figure 2 shows UV-vis-NIR spectra of
226 Y and BETA zeolites after Ni impregnation. In the UV-visible region (from 200 to 800 nm), all
227 catalysts present bands centered at 270, 380, 420 and 720 nm, all of them characteristics of NiO
228 species. The band centered at the lowest wavelength is assigned to $O^{2-} \rightarrow Ni^{2+}$ metal to ligand
229 charge transfer, while the bands at intermediate and high wavelengths are assigned to d-d
230 electron transitions of Ni^{2+} in octahedral coordination inside NiO [230]. In addition, two bands
231 centered at 450 and 635 nm can be distinguished which correspond to d-d electron transitions
232 of Ni^{2+} exchanged in tetrahedral coordination inside zeolite framework [241-263]. The green
233 Ni/H-Y catalyst also presents bands at 670 and 750 nm, not so clearly detected in other samples
234 and which are assigned to d-d electron transition of Ni^{2+} ions in octahedral coordination [2118,
235 274, 285]. However, the presence of this Ni species cannot be disregarded for the latter samples.

236 FIGURE 2

237 On the other hand, other two bands can be observed in the NIR domain (from 800 to 2500 nm).
238 The wide band centered at 1150 nm is attributed to the ν_1 (${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$) transition of octahedrally
239 coordinated Ni^{2+} and appears in all spectra of prepared samples indicating the presence of NiO.
240 In contrast, the last band centered at 1410 nm is related to vibrations of surface hydroxyl groups
241 of zeolite supports [296] and, as expected, is less intense for Ni/Na-zeolite catalysts than for
242 Ni/H-zeolite catalysts.

243 The redox properties of the prepared samples were examined by H_2 -TPR technique in order to
244 analyze the reducibility of different nickel species dispersed on each zeolite. Figure 3a and Figure
245 3b show the H_2 -TPR runs for Ni/Y and Ni/BETA catalysts, respectively. In line with UV-vis-NIR
246 results, the appearance of several peaks in TPR spectra indicates the presence of various Ni
247 species with different reducibility. On the one hand, four defined H_2 consumption peaks can be
248 observed for Ni/H-Y catalyst (Figure 3a). The peak at lowest temperature (450 °C) can be
249 attributed to reduction of surface NiO particles interacting with the zeolitic support, whereas
250 peaks located at 520 and 645 °C are attributed to reduction of tetrahedrally coordinated Ni^{2+}

251 species located on supercages and sodalite cages, respectively [2219, 274, 285, 3027, 3128]. The
252 peak at highest temperature, with a maximum at 730 °C, is related to reduction of octahedrally
253 coordinated Ni²⁺ exchanged in hexagonal prisms, as was confirmed by UV-visible. On the other
254 hand, a new peak can be distinguished at 385 °C for Ni/Na-Y catalyst. The position of this
255 reduction peak is similar to the observed in the nickel oxide sample (insight Figure 3a), so it is
256 associated with reduction of NiO particles weakly interacting with Na-Y zeolite and located in
257 the external surface e of Na-Y zeolite. The shift to lower temperature of H₂-TPR profile reveals
258 that Ni/Na-Y is a more easily reducible catalyst than Ni/H-Y catalyst. This fact is related to the
259 donation of electrons from Na⁺ to nickel [2118]. ~~Ni²⁺ species reducible at temperatures below~~
260 ~~500 °C were quantified in last column of Table 2, where it can be observed that the amount of~~
261 ~~reducible Ni²⁺ increases from 32.2% to 93.2% when Na⁺ is exchanged in the zeolite. This is related~~
262 ~~to the donation of electrons from Na⁺ to nickel [18].~~

263 FIGURE 3

264 Focusing on BETA supported catalysts (Figure 3b), unlike zeolite H-Y, BETA zeolite is not formed
265 by cavities: its structure consists of a three-dimensional system of channels, so nickel location is
266 different to that observed in the zeolite Y. For Ni/BETA catalysts four H₂ reduction peaks are also
267 observed. The peaks at lowest temperatures, with maximums located close to 400 and 450 °C,
268 are related to reduction of NiO with different interaction degree with the support. The first peak
269 at the lowest temperature is attributed to reduction of NiO placed on the outer surface while
270 the second peak is assigned to reduction of certain population of NiO clusters with smaller size
271 and higher interaction with the support [230, 3229, 330]. In contrast, peaks at highest
272 temperatures indicate the presence of Ni²⁺ located at different sites: the peak centered around
273 560 °C is related to reduction of pseudo-tetrahedral Ni²⁺, whereas the peak located between
274 620 and 655 °C is related to Ni²⁺ in hexagonal prisms [252, 263, 341-363]. In line with Y zeolite
275 based catalysts, shift of TPR profile to lower temperatures can be observed in Ni/Na-BETA due
276 to the above mentioned effect, increasing the amount of Ni²⁺ species reducible at temperatures
277 below 500 °C from 47.6% to 79.0% after Na⁺ incorporation.

278 With the aim of quantifying the amount of Ni²⁺ reducible at temperatures below 500 °C,
279 additional TPR tests of reduced samples were carried out (Figure S2). The pre-reduction was
280 done under the same conditions used for the reductions prior to the activity tests: 500 °C for 1h
281 with 20% H₂/He. As expected, TPR profiles of all catalysts exhibited a single H₂ consumption peak
282 between 600 and 700 °C, which is associated with reduction of exchanged nickel. The amount
283 of reduced nickel during pre-reduction process is quantified in the last column of Table 2. Note
284 that the percentage of reducible Ni²⁺ is above 90% for all catalysts, except for Ni/H-Y (43%),

285 [which showed a notable peak at 680 °C. This means that almost all nickel is getting reduced](#)
286 [during activity tests for Ni/Na-Y, Ni/H-BETA and Ni/Na-BETA catalysts.](#) Finally, it is worth to
287 mention that calculated H₂/NiO ratios are between 0.9 and 1.1 for all the prepared catalysts,
288 [i.e., what means that](#) Ni²⁺ is the only reducible specie.

289 3.1.2. CO₂ methanation tests

290 The performances of the prepared catalysts were evaluated by analyzing the obtained CO₂
291 conversions and CH₄ yields. It must be noted that, in all cases, CO was the only secondary
292 product and that the carbon balance closed within ±5%. First, Figure 4 compares the catalytic
293 activity at increasing temperatures of protonic and sodium zeolites containing Ni. As a general
294 trend, it can be clearly noticed that the presence of exchanged Na⁺ in both zeolitic frameworks
295 leads to greater CO₂ conversions in the range of studied temperatures. This effect is more
296 pronounced for Y zeolite supported samples. In fact, the light-off T₅₀ curve of Ni/Na-Y catalyst
297 shifts 30 °C to lower temperatures, while light-off curve of Ni/Na-BETA catalyst is only shifted 15
298 °C. The greater activity of these catalysts, as already explained in H₂-TPR section (Figure 34), is
299 not only in line with the reducibility enhancement but also with the presence of weak CO₂
300 adsorption sites in Na-based catalysts. According to previous studies, the interaction between
301 CO₂ and the support is improved by the presence of the alkali metal, resulting in a promoted
302 CO₂ activation [2148].

303 FIGURE 4

304 By comparing CO₂ conversions of Na⁺ free catalysts, greater activity is found for the Ni/H-BETA
305 catalyst. On the one hand, Ni/H-Y sample (T₅₀ = 415 °C) contains more internally located Ni
306 species providing higher metal dispersion; however, Ni/H-BETA (T₅₀ = 393 °C) sample presents a
307 greater amount of reducible Ni species at 500 °C (47.695% vs. 32.243%) which are considered
308 the active phase for CO₂ methanation [274, 374]. Therefore, the higher activity of Ni/H-BETA
309 catalysts could be related to a larger available Ni⁰ area during methanation reaction, as revealed
310 H₂-TPR results shown in Figure 352.

311 In contrast, when comparing Na-exchanged supported catalysts, similar CO₂ conversions are
312 observed in all range of studied temperatures. In both cases, 50% of CO₂ conversion occurs
313 around 380 °C and the maximum CO₂ conversions are reached at 450 °C (X_{CO₂} = 73%). Although
314 Ni/Na-Y catalyst has greater reducibility, according to the H₂-TPR results, Ni/Na-BETA catalyst
315 contains more ~~reducible NiO~~/Ni²⁺ species inside the framework which could provide higher
316 dispersion. Therefore, the same CO₂ methanation activity shown by both catalysts is explained
317 by the presence of similar available surface of active phase during reaction.

318 ~~Products-C-species~~ distribution at the reactor exit ~~3 different reaction temperatures~~ for the
319 prepared catalysts is illustrated in Figure 5. It can be observed that ~~increasing the reaction~~
320 ~~temperature higher CH₄ yield is achieved. In fact, highest CH₄ productions are reached at 450 °C~~
321 the highest CH₄ yield is reached at 450 °C, being Na⁺ containing catalysts more productive than
322 Ni/H-zeolite catalysts. CO yield, on the contrary, is somewhat ~~superior-lower~~ for Ni/H-zeolite
323 catalysts at 350 °C and ~~reaches maximum values~~ somewhat higher at 400 °C. Regardless the
324 reaction temperature, methane yield of the samples reflects the following order: Ni/Na-BETA >
325 Ni/Na-Y > Ni/H-BETA > Ni/H-Y. Thus, Ni/Na-BETA catalyst results in the more active and
326 productive catalyst, showing maximum CO₂ conversion and CH₄ yield values of 73 and 71%,
327 respectively. Indeed, the best catalytic performance of this catalyst is attributed to the enhanced
328 CO₂ adsorption and to the higher dispersion of reducible Ni species.

329

FIGURE 5

330 *3.2. Effect of La₂O₃ addition*

331 3.2.1. Characterization

332 XRD spectra of calcined and reduced Ni/Na-BETA-supported Ni catalysts after the impregnation
333 of different amounts of La₂O₃ (5, 10 and 15%) are displayed in Figure 6. ~~In all cases,~~ XRD
334 ~~diffraction spectra of calcined catalysts show~~ peaks at 37.3, 43.3 and 62.9° 2θ ~~are observed~~
335 ~~indicating the presence of NiO or bunsenite phase,~~ whereas spectra of reduced catalysts show
336 peaks at 44.3 and 51.7 ° 2θ. The former correspond to NiO (bunsenite phase), while the latter
337 are characteristic of elemental Ni. However, the absence of La₂O₃ characteristic diffraction peaks
338 at 30.0, 39.5 and 46.1° 2θ corresponding to La₂O₃ ~~phase reveals-suggests a high dispersion of~~
339 ~~La₂O₃ or~~ the formation of an amorphous phase. In fact, the XRD backgrounds of La containing
340 samples are lifted in 25-35 ° 2θ region with respect to Na-BETA sample, indicating a greater
341 proportion of amorphous material.

342

FIGURE 6

343 Table 3 shows Ni⁰ crystallite sizes of La-containing catalysts calculated by the Scherrer equation.
344 It can be noticed that Ni dispersion increases with the addition of La₂O₃ loadings; i.e., the higher
345 the content of La₂O₃, the smaller the Ni⁰ crystallite size. In fact, the addition of 15% of La₂O₃ to
346 the Ni/Na-BETA catalyst reduces the surface Ni⁰ crystallite size from ~~21.2~~ 20.1 to 7.47.1 nm,
347 providing higher active phase dispersions, since La₂O₃ acts as a thermal stabilizer of Ni [74, 385,
348 396]

349

TABLE 3

350 N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K of La-containing Ni/Na-BETA catalysts, as well as
351 isotherms of Na-BETA support are included in Figure S2-S3 (Supplementary Material). Similar
352 isotherm shapes are observed in all cases (type I and type IV isotherms combination), suggesting
353 that lanthana addition does not modify considerably the textural properties of Na-BETA zeolite.
354 The external surface areas together with pore volumes are summarized in Table 3. It can be
355 observed that impregnation of increasing loadings of La₂O₃ results in a progressive decrease of
356 the external surface area, which means that impregnated lanthana is located in the outer surface
357 of the zeolite. In fact, external surface area decreases from 224.9 m²·g⁻¹ in the Na-BETA catalyst
358 down to 132.6 m²·g⁻¹ in the 15% lanthana impregnated catalyst. In the same line, specific surface
359 area also decreases with metal content, as it can be observed in Figure 7. On the other hand,
360 regarding the pore volume, a similar trend is observed: the higher the metallic load supported
361 on the zeolite, the lower the pore volume, due to a partial blockage of pores [2219, 230, 4037]. It
362 is worth to mention that almost no difference can be observed between 15% and 10% La₂O₃
363 loaded catalysts.

364 **FIGURE 7**

365 The basicity of different La₂O₃/Na-BETA samples was measured by TPD using CO₂ as probe gas.
366 CO₂-TPD profiles in Figure 8 shows that all these samples contain different CO₂ desorption sites.
367 According to desorption temperature, three different basic sites are detected: weak (T < 150 °C),
368 medium (T = 150-550 °C) and strong (T > 550 °C) [74, 4138, 4239]. For 5%La₂O₃/Na-BETA sample,
369 two peaks centered at 100 and 190 °C are observed, which are attributed to CO₂ desorption
370 from weak (surface OH⁻) and medium (acid-base Lewis pairs) basic sites, whereas samples with
371 10 and 15% of La₂O₃ present one additional peak centered at 640 °C, which is assigned to bulk
372 carbonate decomposition [430]. However, this strongly attached CO₂ does not participate in the
373 CO₂ methanation, since it is desorbed at temperatures above those of reaction. CO₂ desorption
374 quantification obtained from TPD spectra reveal that lanthana impregnation over Na-BETA
375 results in a considerable increase of the surface basicity due to the formation of new basic sites
376 with different strength. Thus, the higher the La₂O₃ content, the higher the number and strength
377 of basic sites.

378 **FIGURE 8**

379 The effect of La₂O₃ addition on distribution and reducibility of Ni species dispersed on the
380 catalysts was determined by H₂-TPR. Before carrying out these experiments, catalysts were
381 degasified for 30 min with 5%O₂/He at 500 °C in order to remove weakly chemisorbed CO₂. Then,
382 H₂ consumption was followed by a TCD detector and, additionally, strongly attached CO₂

383 desorption was followed by mass spectrometry. The H₂-TPR spectra and CO₂ MS profiles of
384 samples with different lanthana content are shown in Figure 9. Below 500 °C, a main H₂
385 consumption peak with a maximum close to 400 °C is observed for all catalysts, which is
386 attributed to reduction of NiO located in the external surface of the zeolite [329, 330]. Above
387 500 °C, in contrast, above 500 °C, the growing mass 44 MS-signal is (drawn in dashed lines,
388 ~~confirming~~ confirms strongly attached CO₂ desorption and hence, the recorded TCD signal
389 cannot be attributed only to H₂ consumption. Nevertheless, the peak appearing above 600 °C is
390 also related to reduction of Ni²⁺ located inside BEA framework [363].

391 FIGURE 9

392 When comparing H₂-TPR profiles of the lanthana based catalysts, a shift to higher temperatures
393 with increasing the La₂O₃ loading is observed. This suggests that the presence of La₂O₃
394 strengthens the interaction between nickel and the support, due to an increase of the nickel
395 polarization [385, 441]. ~~The amount of Ni²⁺ reducible at temperatures below 500 °C is also~~
396 ~~summarized in the last column of Table 3. From the total amount of Ni²⁺, calculated by XRF, From~~
397 ~~integration of TPR profiles up to 500 °C, the reducibility of the samples the percentage of~~
398 ~~reducible nickel species at 500 °C~~ was estimated and reflects this order: Ni/5La₂O₃/Na-BETA
399 (89% of Ni⁰) > Ni/10La₂O₃/Na-BETA (87% of Ni⁰) > Ni/15La₂O₃/Na-BETA (74% of Ni⁰). Therefore,
400 the 10% La₂O₃ loaded catalyst presents the highest reducibility. Note that H₂/NiO values are
401 above the stoichiometric ratio, among 1.1 and 1.4, since CO₂ is desorbed during H₂-TPR tests, as
402 demonstrated in Figure 9.

403 In order to analyze the nature and surface distribution of La and Ni species, XPS measurements
404 were carried out. Figures 10a and 10b show XPS spectra corresponding to Ni 2p and La 3d core
405 levels for fresh and used catalysts, respectively. First, for fresh Ni/Na-BETA catalyst (insight
406 Figure 10a), Ni 2p_{3/2} region reveals two peaks at ≈ 854.5 and ≈ 857 eV together with a broad
407 shake-up satellite peak at ≈ 862 eV. The main peak at lowest binding energies is attributed to
408 NiO weakly interacting with Na-BETA zeolite, whereas the second one corresponds to the Ni²⁺
409 cation in exchangeable positions [252, 452]. No peak corresponding to reduced nickel (Ni⁰) at ≈
410 853 eV was detected. On the other hand, La₂O₃ addition to Ni/Na-BETA catalysts reveals a new
411 main peak in the La3d_{5/2} region at ≈ 835.7 and a satellite peak at ≈ 838.9 eV. Note that these
412 peaks, assigned to supported La³⁺ [4138], intensify with La₂O₃ content, which indicates a
413 progressive increase of the La on the surface. Additionally, a main peak at ≈ 852.4 eV together
414 with its satellite peak at 856.3 are shown in La 3d_{3/2} - Ni 2p_{3/2} region, also corresponding to La³⁺.
415 Regardless the amount of La added in the catalysts, XPS spectra recorded after reaction showed
416 similar binding energies of La³⁺, i.e., La₂O₃ does not suffer from relevant changes after reaction

417 and no Ni⁰ was observed, which indicates that nickel is easily passivated after reaction at
418 ambient temperature [463] (see insight Figure 10b).

419

FIGURE 10

420 From integration of XPS spectra, surface carbon content as well as Ni/Si and Ni/La atomic ratios
421 of fresh and used Ni-La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts were calculated and data is summarized in Table
422 4. It should be noticed that the content of surface carbon remains similar after reaction in all
423 cases suggesting that no coke was formed during reaction tests. As deduced from Table 4, Ni/Si
424 and La/Si atomic ratios increase with La₂O₃ content, i.e., La₂O₃ addition improves NiO dispersion.
425 This trend is in agreement with XRD results according to which a decrease of NiO crystallite size
426 with La₂O₃ loading was observed. Finally, samples submitted to reaction suffer from a slight
427 decrease of Ni/Si ratio and a small increase of La/Si ratio, probably due to Ni sintering during
428 catalytic tests.

429

TABLE 4

430 The effect of lanthana on nickel dispersion was also analyzed by transmission electron
431 microscopy. Figures 11a and 11d show TEM micrographs of reduced Ni/Na-BETA and Ni-
432 10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts, respectively. Unlike lanthana particles, in those images, Ni particles
433 are clearly observable. Notice that no changes occur in the morphology of nickel particle
434 (spherical) with the impregnation of 10% of La₂O₃. Nevertheless, changes in the particle size
435 distribution are observed (visualized and calculated from at least 100 particles of several TEM
436 images), being the distribution notably narrower for La containing sample. This suggests that
437 lantana, as structural promoter, controls the growth of nickel particle during calcination. Indeed,
438 smaller Ni particles are observed for Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA, as it presents an average particle size
439 of 10.1 nm (close to the 10.4 nm observed in Table 3 for the same catalyst estimated by Scherrer
440 equation), whereas in Ni/Na-BETA catalyst an average of 17.7 nm can be observed (similar to
441 20.1 nm presented in Table 2, again estimated by Scherrer equation). Therefore, in agreement
442 with XRD and XPS results, lanthana addition enhances nickel dispersion.

443 ~~The effect of lanthana on nickel dispersion was also analyzed by transmission electron~~
444 ~~microscopy. Figures 11a and 11d show TEM micrographs of reduced Ni/Na-BETA and Ni-~~
445 ~~10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts, respectively. Unlike lanthana particles, in those images, Ni particles~~
446 ~~are clearly observable. Notice that no changes occur in the morphology of nickel particle~~
447 ~~(spherical) with the impregnation of 10% of La₂O₃. Nevertheless, changes in particle size~~
448 ~~distribution are observed (visualized and calculated from several TEM images), being the~~
449 ~~distribution notably narrower for La containing sample. This suggests that lantana, as structural~~

450 ~~promoter, controls the growth of nickel particle during calcination. In the same line, smaller Ni~~
451 ~~particles are observed for Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA. It presents an average particle size of 10.1 nm~~
452 ~~(12% of dispersion), whereas Ni/Na-BETA catalyst an average of 17.7 nm (7% of dispersion).~~
453 ~~Therefore, in agreement with XRD and XPS, lanthana addition enhances nickel dispersion.~~

454 As presence of lanthana was not detectable by TEM, additionally, STEM combined with EDX-
455 elemental mapping was performed. This technique is suitable to differentiate between two or
456 more elements, since provides high resolution element mapping. STEM images together with
457 EDX maps of Ni/Na-BETA and Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts are displayed in Figures 11b-11c and
458 11e-11f, respectively. By comparing STEM image and Ni mapping (red colored) of Ni/Na-BETA
459 sample, it is confirmed that Ni is dispersed as spherical particles. Interestingly, EDX map of Ni-
460 10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalyst shows that La (green colored) is homogeneously dispersed partially
461 covering the surface of the zeolite and in close contact with nickel. Similar homogeneous
462 dispersion of ~~supported~~ La₂O₃ supported on Al₂O₃ has already been reported by Z. Boukha et al.
463 [4138].

464 **FIGURE 11**

465 3.2.2. Activity and stability

466 Figure ~~11-12~~ shows the effect of La₂O₃ content on CO₂ conversion and the temperature-
467 dependent equilibrium conversion in a dashed line. The onset temperature for CO₂ methanation
468 is 250 °C and thermodynamic equilibrium is reached for every catalyst. The required
469 temperatures for X_{CO₂} = 50% are 322, 330, 334 and 381°C for Ni-10%La₂O₃, Ni-15%La₂O₃, Ni-
470 5%La₂O₃ and Ni/Na-BETA catalyst, respectively. ~~As general trend, the~~ The progressive-increase
471 in La₂O₃ loading from 5 to 10% leads to higher CO₂ conversions at every temperature, which
472 suggests that the related gain in basicity results in the desired promoter effect. However,
473 although the increase in lanthana nominal content (from 5 to 10%) leads to greater activity,
474 impregnation of La₂O₃ loadings above 10% seems not to be necessary since non enhancement
475 in CO₂ methanation is observed.

476 According to characterization results, the higher CO₂ methanation activity of Ni-10%La₂O₃/Na-
477 BETA catalyst in comparison to Ni/Na-BETA catalyst is related to the greater amount of smaller
478 Ni θ particles (~~10.4~~8.7 against ~~21.2~~20.1 nm) and to the presence of a considerable amount of
479 weak and medium basic sites (16 vs. 1 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$). Also, 10% lanthana loaded catalyst reveals
480 highest ~~percentage of reducible Ni²⁺ species~~reducibility, according to H₂-TPR results. On the
481 other hand, the slight decrease in catalytic activity observed for Ni-15%La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalyst
482 is associated with the lower textural properties and reducibility shown in ~~Table 3~~Figure 9.

FIGURE 1112

In Figure 132 the products-C-species distribution at 300, 350 and 400 °C is shown for Ni/Na-BETA and Ni-10%La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts. As in the case of Ni/zeolite catalysts, CO from RWGS was the only detected by-product being the carbon balance closed between 95 – 105%. It can be observed that CH₄ yield is increased and that CO yield is considerably reduced by addition of 10% of La₂O₃ for all studied temperatures. The greatest difference among product yields occurs at the reaction temperature of 350 °C: CH₄ yield increases from 30 to 65%, whereas CO yield decreases from 4 to 0.4%. In line with characterization results, the better catalytic performance observed in lanthana containing catalyst is related to a higher amount of active sites where CO₂ can be adsorbed, dissociated and then hydrogenated to methane, according to dissociative mechanism [374]. Moreover, according to Wierzbicki et al. [7, 47], lanthanum addition not only provides new medium strength basic sites, but also modifies Ni properties enhancing its CO₂ adsorption capacity [44, 45]. Therefore, it can be concluded that La₂O₃ addition clearly promotes the CO₂ conversion and the CH₄ yield.

FIGURE 1213

Activity comparison between catalysts prepared in this work with others recently reported in literature is shown in Table 5 [58, 96, 274, 474]. In general, it can be observed that the addition of a promoter enhances notably the catalytic activity for each formulation. For instance, the addition of V₂O₅ to Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts improves considerably nickel dispersion and prevents coke deposition [85], whereas CeO₂ impregnation on Ni/MCM-41 catalyst results in additional CO₂ activation leading to higher conversion [96]. I. Graça et al. studied the performance of a formulation analogous to ours, using CeO₂ (redox promoter) instead of La₂O₃ (structural promoter) and Y zeolite instead of BETA zeolite. It can be observed that activity of the promoted catalysts (14Ni-7Ce/USY and 10Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA) is similar, being slightly lower for 14Ni-7Ce/USY catalyst due to a smaller spacial time (W/FA₀).

TABLE 5

Finally, the stability of the most active catalyst was evaluated after 24h on stream at 350 °C (see Figure 143). Note that CO₂ conversion decreases slightly with time. This deactivation could be related to both active site sintering and coke formation. The second hypothesis was dismissed carrying out a thermo-gravimetric test in 5%O₂/He of the aged catalyst according to which no relevant loss of mass was observed related to coke oxidation (not shown). After 10h-on-stream, anyway, it seems that catalytic activity remains quite stable since similar CO₂ conversions are

515 observed. In addition, the catalyst is very stable in terms of selectivity: non decrease in CH₄
516 selectivity is observed after 24 h on stream.

517
518

FIGURE 1314

519 4. Conclusions

520 The catalytic performance of Y- and BETA-zeolites supported Ni catalysts for CO₂ methanation
521 has been compared and additionally, the effect of La₂O₃ addition as promoter has been
522 evaluated.

523 The reducibility and dispersion of Ni species play an important role in CO₂ methanation: the
524 higher the value of these properties, the better the catalytic performance. Ni is more dispersed
525 in the form of NiO and Ni²⁺ species on H-Y than on H-BETA due to its higher crystallinity and a
526 more accessible framework. However, the reducibility of Ni is higher in the Ni/H-BETA than in
527 the Ni/H-Y catalyst due to a major proportion of NiO species located on the outer surface of the
528 catalyst. After reduction at 500 °C, H-BETA zeolite supported Ni catalysts present a higher
529 surface of reduced nickel (the active phase for CO₂ methanation) and hence, this leads to a
530 superior activity and selectivity.

531 Neutralization of both Y- and BETA-zeolites by addition of exchanged Na⁺ improves the catalytic
532 performance (T₅₀ decreases in 30 and 15 °C, respectively). This enhancement is not only due to
533 a greater reducibility, but also to the generation of some weak basicity that improves CO₂
534 adsorption over the zeolite. Although not big differences in CO₂ conversions are observed
535 comparing Ni/Na-Y and Ni/Na-BETA catalysts, the latter achieves more selectivity towards CH₄
536 than Ni/Na-Y. Therefore, it can be concluded that Ni/Na-BETA is the best catalyst among those
537 here studied to efficiently carry out the hydrogenation of CO₂ into methane.

538 According to the physicochemical properties of the samples, the addition of increasing loadings
539 of La₂O₃ to Ni-zeolite catalysts promotes dispersion into smaller NiO ~~crystallites~~ particles and
540 improves the CO₂ adsorption capacity of the zeolite. These enhancements in the surface basicity
541 and the Ni dispersion provide a greater amount of both basic and active sites, over which CO₂
542 can be adsorbed and then hydrogenated into CH₄. In fact, double CO₂ conversion with eventually
543 total selectivity towards CH₄ can be achieved especially at low and intermediate temperatures
544 with Ni-10%La₂O₃/Na-BETA, which results in the optimal composition. In contrast, higher loading
545 than 10% La₂O₃ do not achieve additional enhancement of the catalytic performance, since
546 detrimental of the textural properties exceeds the beneficial effect of CO₂ adsorption and

547 hydrogenation sites. After 24 h on stream, this formulation has proven to be quite stable in
548 terms of activity and selectivity.

549

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555

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- 686

688 **Table and Figure Captions.**

689

690 **Table 1.** Nomenclature and chemical composition of the prepared catalysts.

691 **Table 2.** Physico-chemical properties of supports and Ni catalysts.

692 **Table 3.** Physico-chemical properties of Ni-La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts.

693 **Table 4.** Surface composition by XPS of the Ni-La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts, before and after
694 reaction.

695 [Table 5. Comparison between the activity results achieved by the prepared Ni/BETA catalysts](#)
696 [and by those \(unpromoted and promoted\) reported in literature by other authors.](#)

697

698 **Figure 1.** XRD patterns of (a) Y-zeolite supported catalysts [\(calcined and reduced\)](#) and (b) BETA-
699 zeolite supported catalysts [\(calcined and reduced\)](#).

700 **Figure 2.** UV-vis-NIR spectra of Ni/zeolite catalysts.

701 **Figure 3.** TPR profiles of (a) Y-zeolite (protonic and sodium) supported Ni catalysts and (b) BETA-
702 zeolite (protonic and sodium) supported Ni catalysts.

703 **Figure 4.** Effect of temperature on CO₂ conversion for (a) Y-zeolite (protonic and sodium)
704 supported catalysts and (b) BETA-zeolite (protonic and sodium) supported catalysts.

705 **Figure 5.** CO₂ conversion and ~~products~~-C-species distribution [at the reactor exit of for](#) Ni/zeolite
706 catalysts at 350, 400 and 450 °C.

707 **Figure 6.** XRD ~~patterns~~[patterns](#) of [calcined and reduced](#) Ni/Na-BETA catalysts with different
708 content of La₂O₃.

709 **Figure 7.** Effect of lanthana incorporation onto Na-BETA on the specific surface area and pore
710 volume.

711 **Figure 8.** CO₂-TPD profiles of Na-BETA promoted with different lanthana loadings.

712 **Figure 9.** Evolution of H₂-TPR and the MS 44 signal with temperature for La₂O₃-promoted Ni/Na-
713 BETA catalysts.

714 **Figure 10.** XPS spectra for La₂O₃-promoted Ni/Na-BETA catalysts; (a) fresh, (b) after reaction.

715 [Figure 11. TEM micrographs \(a and d\), STEM images \(b and e\) and EDX maps \(c and f\) of Ni/Na-](#)
716 [BETA and Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalysts.](#)

717 **Figure 11.12.** Light-off curves of La₂O₃-promoted Ni/Na-BETA catalysts.

718 **Figure 12.13.** CO₂ conversion and ~~products~~ C-species distribution at the reactor exit ~~of~~ for Ni/Na-
719 BETA and Ni-10La₂O₃/Ni-BETA catalysts at 300, 350 and 400 °C.

720 **Figure 13.14.** Evolution of (a) CO₂ conversion and (b) selectivity to CH₄/CO, with time-on-stream
721 over 24 hours for Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA catalyst.

722

TABLE 1

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Catalyst label	Framework	Si/Al ^a	Na (wt. %) ^a	Ni (wt. %) ^a	La ₂ O ₃ (wt. %) ^a
Ni/H-Y	FAU	2.5	1.4	9.5	-
Ni/Na-Y	FAU	2.6	6.0	9.9	-
Ni/H-BETA	BEA	12.4	0.0	9.2	-
Ni/Na-BETA	BEA	11.9	1.4	9.5	-
Ni-5La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	BEA	12.2	1.4	9.6	3.2
Ni-10La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	BEA	12.7	1.3	7.8	7.4
Ni-15La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	BEA	12.3	1.2	7.3	12.0

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^a Determined by XRF.

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TABLE 2

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Sample	\overline{r}_{Ni} (nm) ^a	S_{BET} (m ² ·g ⁻¹) ^b	V_{micro} (cm ³ ·g ⁻¹) ^c	V_{meso} (cm ³ ·g ⁻¹) ^c	Reducible Ni ²⁺ at 500 °C (%) ^d
H-Y	-	720.5	0.24	0.07	-
Ni/H-Y	16.3 <u>17.0</u>	621.1	0.20	0.10	32.2 <u>43</u>
Na-Y	-	832.1	0.29	0.02	-
Ni/Na-Y	22.7 <u>19.8</u>	665.9	0.22	0.05	93.2 <u>91</u>
H-BETA	-	587.3	0.17	0.60	-
Ni/H-BETA	18.5 <u>19.1</u>	485.3	0.12	0.38	47.6 <u>95</u>
Na-BETA	-	513.6	0.13	0.38	-
Ni/Na-BETA	21.2 <u>20.1</u>	415.7	0.10	0.32	79.0 <u>98</u>

730

^a Estimated by Scherrer equation.

731

^b Calculated by complete BET equation.

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^c Determined by application of t-Plot method.

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^d Calculated from H₂-TPR profiles. Reduction conditions: 500 °C for 1h with 20%H₂/He.

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TABLE 3

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Sample	τ_{Ni} (nm) ^a	S_{EXT} (m ² ·g ⁻¹) ^b	V_{micro} (cm ³ ·g ⁻¹) ^b
Na-BETA	-	224.9	0.13
Ni/Na-BETA	21.2 <u>20.1</u>	191.4	0.1
Ni-5La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	16.2 <u>12.5</u>	156.8	0.09
Ni-10La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	10.4 <u>8.7</u>	142.3	0.08
Ni-15La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	7.4 <u>7.1</u>	132.6	0.07

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^a Estimated by Scherrer equation.

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^b Determined by application of t-Plot method.

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TABLE 4

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Catalyst	Before reaction			After reaction		
	C (at. %)	Ni/Si	La/Si	C, at. %	Ni/Si	La/Si
Ni/Na-BETA	3.0	0.030	-	3.0	0.025	-
Ni-5La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	2.9	0.035	0.012	3.9	0.031	0.013
Ni-10La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	2.8	0.068	0.032	2.4	0.067	0.037
Ni-15La ₂ O ₃ /Na-BETA	3.3	0.110	0.063	2.2	0.086	0.067

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TABLE 5

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<u>Catalyst^a</u>	<u>Total flow</u> <u>cm³·min⁻¹</u>	<u>Feed ratio</u> <u>(H₂/CO₂/Inert)</u>	<u>GHSV (h⁻¹)</u>	<u>W/FA₀</u> <u>(g_{cat}·h·mol⁻¹)</u>	<u>X_{CO₂} at 350 °C</u> <u>(%)</u>	<u>S_{CH₄} at 350 °C</u> <u>(%)</u>	<u>Ref.</u>
<u>20NiO/Al₂O₃</u>	<u>150</u>	<u>12/3/5</u>	<u>NA</u>	<u>1.7</u>	<u>42</u>	<u>97</u>	<u>[8]</u>
<u>20NiO-5V₂O₅/Al₂O₃</u>	<u>150</u>	<u>12/3/5</u>	<u>NA</u>	<u>1.7</u>	<u>76</u>	<u>> 99</u>	<u>[8]</u>
<u>15Ni/MCM-41</u>	<u>250</u>	<u>36/9/10</u>	<u>15000</u>	<u>1.6</u>	<u>50</u>	<u>95</u>	<u>[9]</u>
<u>15Ce-15Ni/MCM-41</u>	<u>250</u>	<u>36/9/10</u>	<u>15000</u>	<u>1.6</u>	<u>60</u>	<u>97</u>	<u>[9]</u>
<u>15Ni-HT</u>	<u>100</u>	<u>12/3/5</u>	<u>12000</u>	<u>ND</u>	<u>74</u>	<u>99</u>	<u>[7]</u>
<u>15Ni₂La-HT</u>	<u>100</u>	<u>12/3/5</u>	<u>12000</u>	<u>ND</u>	<u>78</u>	<u>98</u>	<u>[7]</u>
<u>14Ni/USY</u>	<u>250</u>	<u>36/9/10</u>	<u>43000</u>	<u>1.6</u>	<u>42</u>	<u>93</u>	<u>[27]</u>
<u>14Ni-7Ce/USY</u>	<u>250</u>	<u>36/9/10</u>	<u>43000</u>	<u>1.6</u>	<u>57</u>	<u>> 95</u>	<u>[27]</u>
<u>10Ni/Na-BETA</u>	<u>250</u>	<u>16/4/5</u>	<u>10000</u>	<u>4.7</u>	<u>33</u>	<u>88</u>	<u>This work</u>
<u>10Ni-10La₂O₃/Na-BETA</u>	<u>250</u>	<u>16/4/5</u>	<u>10000</u>	<u>4.7</u>	<u>65</u>	<u>99</u>	<u>This work</u>

751

^aHT = hydrotalcite; MCM-41 = mesostructured silica; USY = ultra-stable Y

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FIGURE 1

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FIGURE 2

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FIGURE 3

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FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

FIGURE 6

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FIGURE 7

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FIGURE 8

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FIGURE 9

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FIGURE 11

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FIGURE 1112

FIGURE 1213

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FIGURE 1314